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CLIMATE RESILIENT AND ENVIRONMENTALLY
SUSTAINABLE TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE,
WITH A FOCUS ON INLAND WATERWAYS

D3.1 Specifications on synchromodal transport management systems, components and services

**CRISTAL - Climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport
infrastructure, with a focus on inland waterways**

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List of abbreviations

3/4/5 PL	3 rd /4 th /5 th Party Logistics
ALICE	Alliance for Logistics Innovation through Collaboration in Europe
B/L	Bill of Lading
DT	Digital Twin
ECDIS	Electronic Chart Display and Information System
ES-RIS	European Standards – River Information Services
ETA	Estimated Time of Arrival
GA	Grand Agreement
HGV	Heavy Goods Vehicle
IT	Information Technology
IWT	Inland Waterway Transport
IWW	Inland Water Ways
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LSP	Logistics Service Providers
MaaS	Mobility as a Service
NtS	Notices to Skippers
PI	Physical Internet
QA	Quality Assurance
R&I	Research and Innovation
SCMS	Synchromodal Corridor Management System
SoA	State of the Art
T&L	Transport & Logistics
TEN-T	Trans-European Transport Network
TEU	Twenty-foot Equivalent Unit
TMS	Transport Management System
UC	Use Case
UI	User Interface
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

The present deliverable defines the main requirements and specifications of a Synchro-modal Corridor Management System for Inland Waterways that will be developed within the project to address the challenges emerging from natural and human caused disruptions. It constitutes the ground basis for the systems and technologies that will be developed or integrated in the following tasks of the WP3, leading to a system that will support the project objectives for increased reliability, resilience and attractiveness of the IWT systems. In order to ensure that the developed system fulfils its purpose, the functionalities and effectiveness regarding these objectives will be tested in the project pilot sites.

The main requirements and specifications of the system were defined through a process of co-definition with the project technical and pilot partners, starting from an extended literature review of the SoA regarding transport concepts and corridor management systems that was followed by a questionnaire survey to the pilot sites. The latter was necessary for getting information about the views and needs of the stakeholders of the Inland Waterways Transport systems in relation to the real-life handling of disruptions in their sites.

The analysis of the collected information resulted in drafting the architecture of the system, a system that includes four main components: one for the early detection of disruptions and notifications, one for the identification and assessment of the impacts of disruption on IWW operations, one for supporting the responsive actions to the disruptions (through the concept of synchro-modality) and finally a components for collecting data for enhancing corridor visibility and support decision and policy-making at regional level. The functionalities of these components are outlined through a set of generic Use Cases that will be specified in the next period through close collaboration with the pilots in order to be tested and guide the development of the system.

Finally, through the analysis of the input provided from the pilot sites, it becomes clear that the IWW stakeholders see a value in the proposed Synchro-modal Corridor Management System and express an expectation that its implementation will provide solutions to several of their identified needs. Moreover, they go a step forward, suggesting additional services that could be added in the future which is a request that will also be considered during the development of the system.

1.1 Introduction

The main goal of the present document is to define the main requirements, specifications and architecture of the Synchro-modal Corridor Management System (SCMS) that will be developed in the context of WP3 of CRISTAL project. The aim of this system is to support the project achieve its objectives for resilience, reliability and attractiveness of the Inland Waterways Transport (IWT) systems as these are described in the GA.

The SCMS is intended to be a system that will aggregate information related to the prediction of natural or human caused disruptions in the inland waterways, assess their operational impacts and timely disseminate this knowledge to stakeholders of the inland waterways transport systems to support their

decision making. To do so, the system is strongly connected to the activities of WP2 and WP5 of the project that will produce the main information that the system will consume. More specifically, the SCMS will receive information from sensors that will be deployed in the pilot sites in the context of WP2, measuring infrastructure and navigability parameters. Moreover, the outputs of the digital twin developed in WP5 for the pilots, will feed SCMS with information about impact estimations and predictions for infrastructure status and navigability. The input from these two main sources of information will be enriched also by other external sources available when necessary. In addition, the SCMS will develop or integrate tools, models and services based on the concept of synchronomodality that will support stakeholders' next step actions for efficiently planning and managing synchronodal (Road-to-INW, Rail-to-INW) passenger and freight operations across their networks as a response to the impacts of disruptions, thus leading to an increase of reliability and system resilience. Finally, feedback information from the system implementation will be collected and processed as part of a regional repository of information (observatory) that will be developed and produce KPIs to support also decision and policy-making at regional level.

In order to achieve its goal of defining the SCMS, the document includes an extensive literature review and SoA analysis of the prevailing transport concepts and transport management systems with a focus on synchronomodality as key driver for achieving the attributes of resilience and reliability. This knowledge is further enriched with information from the pilot sites of the project, bringing the real-life operational needs and problems into the equation and thus leading to the co-definition of the proposed main functionalities, components and services of the SCMS while considering also existing limitations and considerations. Based on the required functionalities, the main architecture of the system has been formulated, detailing on the technical requirements and specifications. Finally, to support the overall design of the system, a set of generic Use Cases of the systems has been developed, that will outline the main functionalities and will showcase the benefits of the proposed system to the IWT systems operation.

In the next period following the submission of this deliverable, the generic Use Cases described will be specified in close collaboration with the project's pilot and technical partners. This will be done considering the planned implementation of technologies and concepts in the pilot sites in order to conclude on the final architecture and specifications of the SCMS that will be developed in the context of the other tasks of WP3.

1.2 Mapping CRISTAL outputs

The purpose of this section is to provide an overview of the alignment of the document to the formal deliverable & corresponding task descriptions included in the GA and thus help the deliverable owners and the reviewers to conclude on the level of achievement of the deliverable/task goals.

Table 1 Alignment of D3.1 content to the corresponding GA deliverable & task(s) descriptions

CRISTAL GA Component Title	CRISTAL GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D3.1 - Specifications on	Defining the main requirements and	Chapters 2, 3, 4 and 5	In chapter 2, a SoA analysis on transport

<p>sychromodal transport management systems, components and services</p>	<p>specifications of the synchro-modal transport management system, its components and services: Use cases and architecture definition and guidelines on international standards.</p>		<p>management systems and concepts is performed, detailing on the prerequisites and requirements for the implementation of the concept of synchromodality.</p> <p>In chapter 3, the general specifications of the Synchromodal Corridor management System are described and a selection of components and services to be included is made.</p> <p>In chapter 4 the overall architecture and technical specifications of the system are defined and presented, together with the system compliance to regulation and standards.</p> <p>In chapter 5, the generic use cases of the Synchromodal Management System are defined.</p>
<p>TASKS</p>			
<p>Subtask 3.1 - SCMS platform main requirements and specifications</p>	<p>This task will define the systems' and components' main requirements, specifications and use cases. It will constitute the ground basis for the systems and technologies to be developed or</p>	<p>Chapters 3, 4 and 5</p>	<p>In subchapters 3.1 and 3.4 the CRISTAL approach on the Synchromodal Corridor Management System is defined based on a literature review and the input from pilot</p>

	<p>integrated in the following tasks. Co-definition with technology providers and pilot site partners and stakeholders of the technical specifications related to the services that will be developed, the standards and the necessary connectors that will be used for supporting the interoperability of the systems involved.</p>		<p>stakeholders, leading to defining the main requirements, components and services of the system.</p> <p>In subtasks 4.1 and 4.2 the technical specifications of the Synchronodal Corridor management System are described based on the services and components defined in chapter 3.</p> <p>In subchapter 5.2, the generic use cases of the Synchronodal Corridor Management System are defined through consultation with the project’s technical and pilot partners.</p>
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1.3 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The present report is divided into six chapters. The first chapter includes the executive summary along with the introductory section, the description of the document structure and the justification of the document alignment to the GA requirements. The second chapter includes a literature review and SoA of Transport Management Systems and the concept of Synchronodality. In the third chapter, the views and needs of the IWW stakeholders with a focus of IWW logistics operations and disruption handling are detailed along with the CRISTAL approach towards serving these needs through the development of a Synchronodal Corridor Management System. The fourth chapter includes the description of the functional specifications as well as the main components technical specifications of the SCMS architecture as these can be defined at this stage of the project. In the fifth chapter, a set of Use Cases regarding the implementation of the SCMS is defined and described, aiming to showcase the added value offering of the SCMS to the IWT systems and to support its development. Finally, the sixth chapter includes the main conclusions that emerged from the work performed in Task 3.1 and describes the future steps for the development of the SCMS. All additional material (e.g., questionnaire) used for drafting this deliverable can be found in the Annex I at the end of the document.

2. Transport management systems and the concept of Sychromodality

2.1 Background remarks

The target of the European hinterland freight transport policy has been focused on enhancing the combined use of more sustainable modes (i.e., rail, inland waterway) [1], reducing the road freight operations [2]. However, the shift from road to intermodal transport is not enough, since intermodality, as well as other similar practices, does not offer sufficient agility in the constantly changing transport environment and vulnerability of demand [1]. European Commission acknowledged those difficulties and proposed an action plan [3], aiming at raising intermodal freight attractiveness through better utilization of infrastructure, integration of the modes, cost reduction, and quality improvement.

To overcome the obstacles, the idea of promoting a transport system that aims in synchronization of intermodal transport services has emerged [1]. Travellers' transport has already utilised solutions that include the option of changing modes, according to availability, network capacity, cost, flexibility, and sustainability [4] [5]. The concept of 'Mobility as a Service' (MaaS) for example, is already applied and offers a personalised mobility solution that combines options from different modes (e.g., public transport, car, bike sharing etc.) and transport providers into a single, comprehensive, and on-demand mobility service, taking into consideration real-time disruptions and passenger needs [4] [6].

Sychromodality is a relative recent concept that has been developed in order to enhance the utilization of intermodal operations, especially in large countries and very long distances. In contrast, a characteristic of the European freight transport network is that many final destinations are in a distance less than 300km [3], which is seen as the lower limit where an intermodal transport is competitive. In those distances, the shift and use of alternative transport modes such as rail or inland waterways is difficult to compete the single road transport, as transshipment costs as well as time consumed are higher [7].

However, environmental awareness and economic pressure, led the European Commission to set the target of 30% modal shift from road freight transport by 2030 and 50% by 2050, to modes such as rail and Inland Waterways (IWW), which are environmentally friendlier and have lower societal impact [8]. The European Technology Platform ALICE (Alliance for Logistics Innovation through Collaboration in Europe) has been launched to develop a roadmap to employ innovative solutions and concepts (e.g. sychromodality, Physical Internet) in logistics and supply chains in Europe, aiming at 30% of improvement of overall logistics operations [9]. The emerging ICTs and the extensive digitalisation advancements, create an opportunity to achieve a higher degree and cost-effective integration in transport systems, which is fundamental in order to synchronize transport operations. Moreover, they could assist to better utilisation of capacities and infrastructure, towards socio-economic and environmental sustainability.

2.2 Transport/Corridor management systems SoA

Transport concepts

The idea of managing freight transport within a network of partners across a geographical corridor, has become increasingly accepted as a component of trade and transport corridor projects [10]. Various definitions have been used to define ‘corridor’ and ‘transport corridor management’. According to [11]:

Corridor: *A largely linear geographic band defined by existing and forecasted travel patterns involving both people and goods. The corridor serves a particular travel market or markets that are affected by similar transportation needs and mobility issues. The corridor includes various networks (e.g., limited access facility, surface arterial(s), transit, bicycle, pedestrian pathway, waterway) that provide similar or complementary transportation functions. Additionally, the corridor includes cross-network connections that permit the individual networks to be readily accessible from each other.*

(Integrated) Corridor Management: *ICM consists of the operational coordination of multiple transportation networks and cross-network connections comprising a corridor and the coordination of institutions responsible for corridor mobility. The goal of ICM is to improve mobility, safety, and other transportation objectives for travellers and goods.*

Similar to the above, is the concept of Green Transport Corridors (GTC), that focuses on the environmental aspect of freight operations and the need to primary reduce climate impact, by implementing sustainable logistics services, advanced ICTs and intermodality concepts [12].

By definition, it is clear that many actors operate in a transport corridor, and they have to work together properly, in order to ensure corridor’s efficiency. These parties might be:

- Governmental bodies responsible for infrastructure (e.g., ports, roads, railways, rivers, border posts) and regulation (transport, customs, immigration, security, health, agriculture, trade etc.)
- Private sector operators (e.g., roads, railways, ports, terminal operations, freight forwarding, cargo clearing, finance).
- Regional communities [11]

Corridor management therefore is a complex process that aims to coordinate all the above parties to improve corridor’s performance. Critical in successful corridor management is the existence of a ‘coordination mechanism’, since otherwise it is difficult to specify the accountable for decisions as well as failures, between the numerous stakeholders. Therefore, institutional and organisational initiatives should be launched [11], as well as governance design and legislative documents [13]. In order to choose the appropriate strategy for effective corridor management, [14] proposes a framework (Figure 1) according to various types of corridors that have been identified in [14].

Figure 1 Choosing Appropriate Management Structure [14]

Transport corridor management improves the efficiency of transport operations in the corridor. Furthermore, synchronizing intermodal freight terminals in a transport corridor, has the following impacts [15]:

- Advanced intermodality and interoperability between modes of transport (with focus on last-mile operations)
- Create common service quality standards in transport corridors and common information system in intermodal transport corridors
- Carries out small and medium container flows
- Organizes the movement of new container modes between intermodal terminals in the corridor [15]

Figure 2 presents the main logistics chain between seaport and hinterland intermodal terminals [15].

Figure 2 The main logistics chain between seaport and hinterland intermodal terminals [15]

Transport Corridors in EU

The importance of corridor management was acknowledged by the EU as key enabler to improve its transport network efficiency and the subsequent economic growth. A multimodal core transport network for Europe has been proposed, as part of the TEN-T, containing two networks:

- The Core Network, which includes the most important connections, linking the most important nodes, and is to be completed by 2030, and
- the Comprehensive Network, which covers all European regions and is to be completed by 2050 [16].

The Trans-European Transport Network (TEN-T) promotes the development of a network of all available transport modes across Europe: railways, roads, inland waterways, maritime shipping, ports, airports and railroad terminals. The ultimate goal is to boost freight transport operations, assisting in strengthen social, economic and territorial cohesion in the EU [16]. The European policy is not just about improving 'hard' infrastructures, but also focuses on the implementation of emerging digital technologies between the corridor's stakeholders, which will serve as a facilitator for an efficient transport corridor management.

Supply chain networks suffer from transparency shortage, mainly due diverse IT-infrastructure and lack of communication between supply chain partners. Furthermore, plain information such as the current status and geographic position of cargo in a supply chain often does not exist or it is not available for partners and logistics service providers, setting the integration of systems to real time monitoring, as a key priority [17]. Four key variables have been identified (except of cost reduction) to be important for

the LSPs platforms [18]: Improved service reliability; the dependence on the LSP; promoting the integration between client-LSPs; fleet and delivery information management provided by an LSP.

The development of the TEN-T as the core network of European transport aims to remove obstacles and confront barriers to enhance supply chains' performance. However, the integration promoted at the TEN-T core network, is not holistic, as the critical alignment of hubs and corridors is missing, particularly for freight transport. Moreover, vertical integration among supply chain requirements of manufacturers, distributors and the wholesalers has not been achieved and therefore the varying customer's needs cannot be properly satisfied [9].

In any case, it is difficult to reach seamless transport. The European logistics network involves numerous operations and stakeholders which operate in many different countries. Thus, integrating those operations in a pan European level is a critical factor to boost European economy. ALICE produced a roadmap to achieve integration via the ultimate goal of Physical Internet, by synchronizing services and equipment on corridors and hubs. ALICE reports that the focus of network integration has been placed on static attributes such as interconnectivity and interoperability, and not on dynamic features, which serve the goals of resilience and responsiveness. According to ALICE 'the absence of common processes, common language and standards for interoperability is a key obstacle to achieving integration' [9]. Moreover, ALICE roadmap suggests that:

- *Adopted technology should be reliable, accessible, low cost and as generic as possible.*
- *Interactions between stakeholders should be easily established and cost benefit.*
- *Supply chains should improve efficiency by providing visibility and collaboration capabilities.*
- *The operational control of transport processes should be optimised through improved synchronisation.*

Hinterland connections are important to improve the transportation efficiency, particularly under the pressure of the increasing freight volumes and the transshipment costs. Moreover, communication and data exchange, are prerequisites for interconnectivity, when the selection of transport mode has to be made. Innovation on digital technologies may support the implementation of freight 'smart solutions' to facilitate the transformation of supply chains into integrated value chains, ensuring their agility, efficiency and cost reduction, as well as breaking isolated operations. Integration of hubs and corridors at all levels (strategic, tactical, operational) should also been supported [9].

Inland Waterway Transport

Europe has over 30,000 km of canals and rivers that link together hundreds of key industrial areas. The core network of around 10,000 km connects the Netherlands, Belgium, Luxembourg, France, Germany, Poland, Czech Republic, Austria, Slovakia, Hungary, Romania and Bulgaria within the EU, with Switzerland, Croatia, Serbia, Moldova and Ukraine outside of the Union. The backbone of this network is major rivers such as the Rhine and the Danube. There are also numerous of smaller rivers and canals that connect a variety of freight modes (industrial centres, hubs and destinations). A considerable number of ports along the network provide access and links with other modes of transport (road, rail, barge, short sea shipping and deep-sea shipping) [19].

Waterway transport and information exchange within river corridor that have been standardized by the European Standard River Information Services (ES-RIS) and the Directive 2005/44/EC on harmonised river information services on the EU's inland waterways, should be closely reviewed [20]. RIS attempts to harmonise information technologies in a traffic management system to facilitate real-time information exchange between modes (barges) and inland infrastructure.

RIS is the concept whereby information services in inland navigation support traffic and transport management in inland navigation, including interfaces with other modes of transport [20]. It aims to have positive impacts on safety, efficiency and environmental burden, of inland navigation. For this purpose, EU adopted a holistic approach that includes policy, legal framework, research, and implementation of the legislation, between the actors involved in the network. Specifically, RIS technology guidelines focuses on Inland Electronic Chart Display and Information System (Inland ECDIS), Notices to Skippers (NTS), inland Automatic Identification System (AIS) and Electronic Reporting International (ERI) [22]. The standards that have been developed are constantly updated. RIS detailed objectives can be summarized as follows [20] [21]:

- Increase safety
- Improve inland navigation efficiency through optimization of information exchange between the nodes of IWW chain (vessels, locks, bridges, terminals and ports)
- Better utilisation of inland waterway infrastructure (providing information on navigability)
- Environmental protection – on time traffic and transport information to better damage control
- Assist integration of IWT into multimodal supply chains through accurate and timely information to support transport management.

The services included in the RIS concept can be indicative summarised as follows:

- Information (e.g., geographical, hydrological, meteorological and traffic related data) on fairways to plan, carry out and monitor transport (e.g., water levels, aids to navigation, fairway information, opening hours of locks etc).
- Traffic information services (information on barges positions) to allow for tactical or strategic planning.
- Traffic management aims at optimising the use of the infrastructure and facilitating safe navigation.
- Calamity abatement services (CAS) are responsible for registering vessels and their transport data at the beginning of a trip and en-route updating. If an accident occurs, the responsible authorities provide the data immediately to the rescue and emergency teams.
- Information for transport management includes estimated times of arrival (ETA's) based on fairway information, allowing to plan resources for port and terminal processes.
- Statistics and customs services: the RIS improves and facilitates the collection of inland waterway statistical data in the Member States.
- Waterway charges and port dues: the travel data of the ship can be used to automatically calculate the charge and initiate the invoicing procedure.

The directive outlines a framework to develop four technical requirements and specifications to [21]:

- harmonised exchange of information between different actors providing RIS
- interaction with other traffic management systems of other transport modes
- interoperable systems for inland waterway transport services
- a framework to develop guidelines and specifications

Implementing Regulation (EU) No 909/2013, as amended by Implementing Regulation (EU) 2018/1973, defines technical specifications for the electronic chart display and information system for inland navigation (Inland ECDIS). Its annex includes detailed specifications for [21]: performance standards; data standards; codes for producers and waterways; presentation standards; operational and performance requirements, methods of testing and required test results; measures to ensure software quality; system configurations.

However, the current concept of RIS, faces the four technical standards in isolation and independent, since they were developed based on a technical and operational focus. The next step for RIS, relies on the update of RIS Directive and aspects such as automation of inland navigation and cybersecurity, and the introduction of digital tools, which may lead to a further development of RIS's standards [20].

2.3 Synchronodal and resilient management concepts of T&L

Multimodality, Intermodality, Co-modality

Transporting goods in various destinations usually involves the use of different transport modes [4]. In multimodal transport, 'several modes of transport are combined to transport freight' [23], while intermodality is referred to 'the technically optimised intermodal transport where intermodal transport units are used (such as containers, semitrailers, etc.) to facilitate the transfer of freight between modes without direct handling of the goods' [23]. Moreover, in intermodal freight, transport goods are transported in one and the same loading unit or vehicle using various modes (i.e., road, rail, water) without any handling of the goods during the transshipment (European Conference of Ministers of Transport, 1993, as cited in [1]). Specifically, in the Economic Commission for Europe (UN/ECE), TERMINOLOGY ON COMBINED TRANSPORT [24], the following definitions are proposed:

Multimodal transport: *Carriage of goods by two or more modes of transport.*

Intermodal transport: *The movement of goods in one and the same loading unit or road vehicle, which uses successively two or more modes of transport without handling the goods themselves in changing modes. By extension, the term intermodality has been used to describe a system of transport whereby two or more modes of transport are used to transport the same loading unit or truck in an integrated manner, without loading or unloading, in a [door to door] transport chain.*

Combined transport: *Intermodal transport where the major part of the European journey is by rail, inland waterways or sea and any initial and/or final legs carried out by road are as short as possible.*

Intermodal transportation underpins the implementation of new operational and business models for transportation and logistics (e.g., City Logistics, Physical Internet, and Synchronomodality) that have been emerged to respond to economic, environmental, and societal needs [25]. Stakeholders' cooperation and integration of operations are key factors for the successful implementation of those initiatives [25], since

transportation network is a complex system. Figure 3 illustrates this complexity, presenting the Social Business Network for an intermodal transportation system of shippers, carriers, customers, facility and infrastructure managers, and institutional authorities, proposed by [25].

Figure 3 Relationships among the main actors in freight transportation systems [25]

According to ALICE synchronomodality builds on co-modality and intermodality concepts, to enhance the alignment between transport services of all modes involved, in order to improve supply chain efficiency levels [9]. Synchronomodality is interrelated and followed by the concept of Physical Internet. Figure 4 summarizes current and emerging concepts and business models in transportation modal choice [26].

Figure 4 Paradigms in transportation modal choice [26]

Synchromodality

Synchromodality is still at starting point [27]. Transport actors raise concerns to employ these types of operations mainly due to unclear financial benefits and hesitations on information sharing [28]. Concerning the definition of the concept, there are various descriptions that can be found in the literature, having however similar traits. Initially, it has been introduced in 2010 by Tavasszy, van der Lugt, and Hagdom [8]. Synchromodality can be defined as a ‘network of well-synchronised and interconnected transportation modes, which together cater for the aggregate transportation demand’ [29]. It is regarded as the next step of freight network evolution that will offer cost reduction and improved quality services, aligned with the European Union vision for smart, green, and integrated transport [29].

An important attribute of synchromodality services, is that it facilitates the transport planning by moving as late as possible the shipment decisions, through informed and flexible planning, booking and management services. So far, the choice of shipment operations - in terms of mode used and routing selection - is made a long time before the transport begins, without taking into consideration last minute changes and available options; even if in some cases such as port-hinterland container transport, features of synchromodality have been used. Synchronization between modal operations is limited or absent. The emerging ICTs and extensive digitalization however, offer considerable opportunities to convert synchromodality from an academic concept into a reliable business model [9].

According to the Dutch Institute for Advanced Logistics (Dinalog) [30] in synchromodal transport a shipper signs a contract with a logistics company that only covers price, time of delivery and level of quality, giving the logistics supplier the freedom and flexibility to choose the modes of transport. Speed, cost reductions and sustainability are advantages that appear to both. Dinalog views that important conditions for promoting synchromodality are coordination, regulations and contracts [30]. While intermodal transport focuses on capacity utilisation of modes to achieve economies of scale, transportation cost reduction and decrease carbon footprint, synchromodality focuses on synergies among stakeholders, services and modes, providing operators with the freedom to choose among multiple alternatives [1].

Synchromodality is also defined as an ‘evolution of inter- and co-modal transport concepts, where stakeholders of the transport chain actively interact within a cooperative network to flexibly plan transport processes and to be able to switch in real-time between transport modes tailored to available resources’ [31]. In this case the consignor defines in advance the principal requirements of the transport such as cost, transportation time and sustainability aspects. As an outcome, high optimization of transport processes can be achieved, as well as increased utilization of available resources. Synchromodal transport thus, leads to an optimal use of all available capacity (Figure 5) [31].

Figure 5 Synchronodality concept [31]

Another important issue that arises in synchronodality is the form of contract/agreement between the shipper and the transport service providers, as well as the ‘ownership’ of the decision. In intermodal transport shipper decides the way that the consignment will be transported based on information provided by service operators (fixed booking). In this case, after the shipment departs, no real-time alternative modal shift can be applied, even if there is available capacity on the network [1]. In most cases, the usual practice is that shipper decides the service line and time of delivery, and the service operator undertakes the necessary transport decision, e.g., routing, terminal of origin/destination, service line, vehicle, and departure time (open path booking). In synchronodal transport the decision is shifted from the shipper to the service provider in order to fully exploit real time information (open mode booking). The shipper determines the delivery time, and assigns all transport decisions to the service operator [1]. The open mode booking in synchronodality focuses particularly on: cost reduction, decrease of emissions, and improvement of service quality when compared to road freight; exploiting capacity utilization of alternative modes and eliminating delays, thus leading to a flexible, reliable and resilience system [1].

Synchronodal transport aims to contribute to a more efficient, reliable, flexible, and sustainable network [28] by promoting close coordination and cooperation of all stakeholders, and building on information sharing, advanced communication technologies, and resilient infrastructure [27]. Synchronodality demands both vertical and horizontal integration (Figure 6). Vertical integration refers to synchronize the operations involved in moving a consignment from the origin point to the destination, and horizontal to unify operations into a single service [32]. Horizontal integration is a founding element of synchronodal transport that facilitates the implementation of real-time planning and switching of modes and routes. Which is also depending, except for information sharing, on infrastructures [28].

Figure 6 Integrated view of freight transport planning [32]

Synchromodality furthermore promotes green freight transport, through the selection and use of modes which emit lower emissions (e.g., IWT, rail) [15]. The real-time decision making and the information sharing, provides optimal utilization of capacity, and thus reduces the danger of bottlenecks in the transport corridors [15]. Table 2 compares the basic attribute of synchromodality, in contrast to multimodal and intermodal transport [28]. Figure 7 visualises the advantages of synchromodality, in contrast to intermodality [90].

Table 2 Comparison of multimodal, intermodal, and synchromodal transport planning [28]

Characteristics	Transport Type		
	Multimodal	Intermodal	Synchromodal
Planning	Before Shipment	Before Shipment	Real-Time
Integration	Vertical	Vertical	Vertical and horizontal
Responsibility of Shipment	Under the full responsibility of one carrier or agent	Partial responsibility by each carrier per segment of shipment	Partial responsibility by each carrier per segment of shipment
Number of Contracts per Shipment	One contract	Multiple contracts	Open contract
Shipping Cost	High	Low	Low
Coordination Cost	Low	High	Low
CO ₂ Emission	High	Low	Low
Mode Shift	Fixed	Flexible before contract	Flexible
Unit of Product	Any unit	Intermodal containers	Any unit
Shipment Distance	Short to long	Long	Short to long

Figure 7 Synchronomodal transportation versus intermodal transportation [90]

As stated before, synchronomodality can increase transport systems' flexibility, reliability and competitiveness, by adopting real-time decision-making processes and fully exploitation of data and information. The new business paradigm of synchronomodality however, requires fundamental changes, such as:

- Ability to make modal choices
- Governance regulations and adjustments
- Standardization
- Mindset shift to real time decision processes rather than predictive and to information sharing [8]

Synchronomodality can be regarded as the implementation of MaaS concept to freight transport, and thus quoted as 'Synchronomodality as a Service—SaaS', since through informed and flexible planning, booking, and management, it allows mode and routing decisions to be made in a single service, on demand, and as late as possible in the transport planning process [9].

Synchronomodal corridor management

Synchronomodal corridor management can be defined 'as the process of integrating the control of the three different modes aiming at orchestrating transport flow in a manner that ensures the efficient utilisation of the network and deals with planned and unplanned disruptions. Synchronomodal corridors, are also referred as green transport corridors, due to their environmental impact [4].

Synchromodal corridor management presents several challenges based on its nature as a complex socio-technical system, comprising a large number of stakeholders. Information sharing in the freight transport network requires consideration of different stakeholders’ demands and a holistic overview. However, the information management among stakeholders in freight corridors is still in its infancy [4].

The advanced collaboration that is needed in synchromodal corridors, such as smart contracts, information sharing, and open databases, can be supported and facilitated by the ICT developments [4]. The concept mostly appears in academic research and the benefits of its implementation may be expected in three areas: consumers (service quality, flexibility, transparency), the environment (sustainability), and industry (cost reduction [4], as shown in Table 3 [4] [9].

Table 3 Expected impact of R&I activities on corridors, hubs, and synchromodality [4] [9]

	Primary Impacts	Secondary Impacts
Consumers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Customer satisfaction + Product availability + Secure transport 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Load factors: weight and cube fill of vehicles + Volume flexibility (Time to +/- capacity). + Route and mode flexibility.
Environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Energy consumption (kWh Logistics/GDP) + Renewable energy source share - CO₂ Emissions (kg CO₂/t.km) + Modal Shift 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Asset utilisation + Supply Chain Visibility. + Reliability of transport schedules + Transport route optimisation (reducing distance) + Transport actors using automatic data exchange
Industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Return on assets - Cargo lost to theft or damage - Total supply chain costs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Cargo and logistics units integrated in the automatic data exchange + Supply Chain Adaptability and Flexibility + Decoupling logistics intensity from GDP. - Waiting time in terminals - Risk factor reduction - End-to-end transportation time. - Lead times

*(+) increase, (-) decrease

Vertical and horizontal integration of actors and services creates an opportunity to ensure system’s sustainability and confront disruption and vulnerability. Information exchange requires not only ICT, but also standardisation of data and harmonisation of information systems, creating new business opportunities [4].

Figure 8 presents the key stakeholders that are involved in multimodal/synchromodal transportation [4], while Figure 9 depicts the interrelationship of supply chain stakeholders with a potential role in synchromodal logistics [27].

Figure 8 Stakeholder relationships in European freight corridors [4]

Figure 9 Logistics stakeholders and their interrelationships [27]

Synchromodal Modelling Operator is a model that has been developed by [1] to analyse and compare intermodal and synchromodal operations from economic, societal, and environmental perspectives. A schematic overview of the model structure is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10 General scheme of Synchronodal Modelling Operator [1]

Synchromodality in the EU

Synchromodality is not well known in most of the European regions (except for Belgium, Netherland and Luxembourg). The goal however and the commitment of EU in decarbonization, poses greater challenges to adopt synchromodality in a pan-European level and promote the use and synergies between environmentally friendly modes (IWT, rail). Figure 11 presents the key aspect of the synchromodal transport [31].

Figure 11 Synchronomodality key aspects [31]

An ultimate goal for Europe’s transport policy is unfold in ALICE roadmap, towards smart and seamless network, aligned with corridors and hubs, by synchronizing services between modes and shippers. Collaboration between actors is vital to implementation of synchronomodal services, and vertical and horizontal integrations is needed. In European level, integration refers to join corridors and hubs in a pan-European, consistent freight network, from TEN-T to last-mile level [9]. ALICE acknowledges the importance of information systems harmonization and the adoption of modern technologies and digitization to create a truly synchronomodal services. Information management (Data matching, Standards, Security, Protection of Confidentiality rights etc.) is viewed as vital. Moreover, ALICE explored the constantly changing priorities of freight customers, and found that reliability is the most important aspect to select a transport service, following by level of price, available capacity, information management, transport time, handling time, frequency of transport and ecological aspects [9].

Physical Internet

Synchronomodality can be viewed as a step to reach the goal of Physical Internet – a concept that has been developed quite parallel [8] - since it also promotes the flexible and real-time modal shift from roads to rails and inland waterways, based on the running availabilities and changing external conditions [9]. The concept of Physical Internet has been evolved in order to face disruptions on supply chains and ensure global logistics sustainability [33] of transport networks in societal, environmental and economic aspects [9]. It was inspired by the operations taking place in the World Wide Web: e.g. when someone sends an email to someone else across the world, it is usually received quickly and seamlessly. The message is divided into packets and goes through a network of hubs/nodes depending on their capacity, until they come together to reach its destination, without the sender be aware of the route it followed [8] [34].

The same approach was proposed for the delivery of physical goods, and thus the term ‘Physical Internet’ arisen: the sender (i.e., shipper) sends the message (shipment), but he/she is not aware of the transmission (transport) process, as the only concern is to reach the final destination (delivery point) in

the preferred quality of service and time. The transportation process exploits the availability of the network nodes (capacities) and routes, in a seamless flow [8]. A core definition that was initially used, states that: ‘PI is an open global logistics system founded on the physical, digital and operational interconnectivity through encapsulation, interfaces and protocols’ [35].

According to ALICE roadmap Physical Internet should be implemented gradually by 2050 (Figure 12) and could be regarded as the most ambitious concept towards efficiency and sustainability in transport logistics, in response to environmental challenges and directives [36].

Figure 12 ALICE roadmap towards zero emissions [37]

Drivers and Challenges

The following aspects have been identified as drivers to speed up synchronodality [31]:

- The fluctuation on fuel pricing and the need for cost savings
- The overburdened road infrastructure
- The increasing environmental awareness of society
- Strict environmental regulations and goals to be achieved, e.g., the reduction of emissions by at least 50% by 2050 compared to 2008.

On the other hands, the implementation of synchronodal services faces significant challenges [31] [4], i.e.:

- Trust among stakeholders to enhance collaboration and cooperation.
- Complexity on planning.

- Connectivity, collaboration and data sharing of existing IT systems
- information exchange
- standards establishment
- the ICTs required to integrate a complex environment of policy barriers, different interests, priorities, and connectivity
- the benefits of synchromodality have not fully exploited and it seems to be still an academic concept [4]

Furthermore, the primary barriers that have been identified are:

- Operational problems such as train decoupling, terminal working hours, use of rail infrastructure for both passenger/freight transport.
- Organizational cooperation problems (e.g., coordination between actors and networking among different partners).
- Economic issues due to higher handling and transshipment cost.
- New business model needed to facilitate integration and synchronized data information sharing.
- unfamiliarity of the actors with the synchromodal concept [4]

The benefits of synchromodality have not been fully exploited yet in practical level, however research has already pointed out an increase in economic and environmental sustainability. Moreover, synchromodality may enhance the sustainability of the whole transport and logistic network, and particularly respond to the vulnerability of demand, by adopting a real time planning procedure [4].

In short, the benefits originating from the application of synchromodal services are [31]:

- Advanced flexibility in transport choices
- Better utilization of rail and inland waterway
- Optimization of network capacity, and
- Reduction in carbon footprint

To explore the benefits of synchromodality, the Synchromodal Modelling Operator is a model that has been developed by [1] to analyse and compare intermodal and synchromodal operations from economic, societal, and environmental perspectives. The model embraces road and rail freight, as well as inland waterway transport. Available modes are direct-road transport, intermodal rail transport, and intermodal inland waterway transport. The model generates the indicators presented in Table 4.

Table 4 Comparison of multimodal, intermodal, and synchromodal transport planning [1]

Impacts	Indicators
Economic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total system costs, and cost composition (including haulage costs, handling costs, and value losses of freight and vehicles) • Total system time expense, and time composition (including initial waiting time at the port, haulage time, handling time, and transfer/transshipment time at terminals)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capacity occupancies of service lines
Societal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Network flows, and flow concentration (Reduction in) Road traffic, both as direct-road transport and as pre- and end-haulage
Environmental	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Emissions (carbon dioxide emissions)

The research [1] points out interesting results concerning the benefits on synchronomodality versus intermodality. In terms of direct economic benefit there is no significant difference since synchronomodal transport has lower freight transport costs, but higher handling ones, due to the need of more often change of modes. However, the model revealed a 10% increase in capacity utilisation and 8% reduced delivery times, enhancing the view that synchronomodality may increase service quality. The advantages of synchronomodality are clearer in terms of society and environment. It was noted that it is responsible for a modal shift from road to rail (road transport reduction up to 16%) that leads to a significant CO₂ reduction (approximately 30%). The synchronized operations furthermore facilitate the use of sustainable modes in shorter distances as they increase their competitiveness in contrast to direct road transport. This modal shift however increases the truck traffic close to the hinterland destination terminals [1].

Critical success factors

Based on literature reviews and interviews with experts in the transportation sector, the following critical success factors have been identified [27]:

- Network, collaboration, and trust.
- Sophisticated and dynamic planning.
- Utilisation of digital technologies, secured information and clarification of accessibility rights.
- Update physical infrastructure supporting smart operations.
- Legal, political framework, and updated regulation for emerging issues (e.g., the liability in a case of loss, damage, or delay when shifting modes in synchronomodal networks, or the need to secure sensitive information).
- Awareness and mental shift of all stakeholders to understand the importance of sustainability and efficiency of the entire network in order to be able to react when disruptions occur. Moreover, the handling of decision making to other service operators needs a new way of business thinking.
- Pricing/cost/service pricing services are more complex because costs are relative to the selected modes.

Table 5 presents the critical success factors, and the technologies that affect each factor [27].

Table 5 Critical success factors and enabling technologies [27]

		Critical success factors					
		Network collaboration and trust	Sophisticated planning	Physical infrastructure	Legal and political framework	Awareness and mental shift	Pricing, cost, service
Enabling technologies	Traceability	ü			ü		
	Intelligent systems		ü	ü			
	Data analysis		ü			ü	ü
	Optimization		ü	ü			ü
	Simulation	ü	ü	ü		ü	
	Integration platforms	ü			ü	ü	ü

ISOLA project [38] investigated three vertical aspects of synchromodal transport integration: The willingness of shipper to assign the transport services; develop a model for capacity management; and how information management will reduce overall costs. According to [26] modal control, flexibility and value-added services are perceived as the most important factors that a shipper may take into consideration in order to move to adopt synchromodal services. The research [26] revealed that modal control is crucial and shippers will assign it easier, if they will get better service quality and lower cost, take advantage of the ability to swift modes during transport, and have ancillary services beyond the basic transportation service. Specifically, more than 68% of the shippers are willing to assign their modal control, in order to take advantage of better service or price. Also, shippers are willing to employ synchromodal services in order to ensure flexibility, due to unstable and vulnerable demand [38].

Moreover, as one of the key elements of synchromodality is to optimize transport network by shifting freight operations to IWT, special attention should be placed upon the corridors' (rivers, tributaries canals etc.) operations, since there are a lot of disruptions that discourage potential users. A synchromodal approach should take into consideration those special issues, in order to provide solutions to strengthen transport network's resilience. According to [91] there are four types of accidents, i.e. allusion, collision, grounding, hull/machinery/equipment damage, other accidents registered (e.g. capsized, shipwreck, foundering etc.), and four causes of accidents, i.e. human failures, technical faults, weather conditions, operational cause, other causes. Figure 13 depicts the main causes of water transportation accidents and disruptions [92], [93], [94].

Figure 13 Causes of water transportation accidents and disruptions ([37] adapted for CRISTAL)

2.4 The way to synchromodality as a guiding principle for the SCMS development

Synchromodality can be regarded as real-time, dynamic and optimised intermodal transportation. ALICE suggest that ‘the increasing pressure for the deployment of innovative solutions for responsive, customized and sustainable freight transport service throughout Europe’, is the primary factor towards adopting synchromodality practices. The European focus is changing from Intermodality, to co-modality, to the latest concept of Synchromodality and Physical Internet, where all transport options are available according to destination, time needed, and sustainability concerns [9]. However, transport and logistics chains should be further enhanced by embracing in the network IWT and hinterland connections, considering the constantly increasing freight volume and the transshipment costs.

The environmental awareness and strict targets that have been set internationally, promote synchromodality as being a step towards a more sustainable and resilient freight transport system [4]. In order to deliver synchromodality, three elements need special attention:

1. Developing a single point of transport services (horizontal integration) [29]
2. Information and data sharing of involved actors to improve efficiency and ensure sustainability [39]
3. Real time modal selection and shift to enhance system’s flexibility and reliability [40]

For the adoption of synchromodal transportation concepts, it is crucial to modify the decision-making processes towards information sharing with critical infrastructure users. The development of synchromodal network management would be easier to achieved if it follows a step-by-step process, from a more collaborative disruption management to a synchromodal corridor manager that has control over the modes and enables the synchronisation of services based on demand [4] [9].

Table 6 presents the six pathways that have been identified in the ALICE roadmap [9], and for every pathway the main innovations needed, the using market and the expected impact.

Table 6 Roadmap pathways [9]

Pathway	Main innovations	Using Market	Expected Impact
1. Understanding the demand for synchromodal transport	Detailed demand mapping and forecasting tools. Big data used for demand prediction.	Transport service providers, SME networks.	Load based, a-modal planning and booking possible due to demand intel.
2. Optimize alignment supply chains and synchromodal / multimodal services	Tactics for transport service and supply chain alignment (e.g., hybrid networks). Mind shift.	Supply chain managers, Logistics managers, Regulators.	Tightly coupled production/ distribution/ transport systems.
3. New roles for hubs in the supply chain	New value-added business models. Hubs taking role in supply chains for e.g., postponed manufacturing.	Real estate, cluster managers, transport service providers, port authorities, Regulators.	Healthy and stable clusters, networks of clusters. Specialisation of hubs in TEN-T.
4. An integrative freight network strategy	European core freight network and access networks, multimodal network management, freight ITS	Network managers, corridor managers, hub managers	Connected and sustainable Pan-European freight TEN-T infrastructure
5. Transport chain design and operation for Synchromodality	Seamless and transparent freight service networks in Europe (gateway networks, hub/spoke, plus service levels	Transport service providers, hub operators	Increased diversity and resilience of transport services, more Intermodality.
6. Deploying ICT as integrating technology	Extended freight ITS towards Integrated and automated planning, booking, operation	ICT sector, Transport service providers	Automated and responsive synchromodal transport services.

To summarize, synchromodality aims to develop more efficient, reliable, flexible, and sustainable transport networks, contributing to the decrease of emissions by shifting freight to environmental friendlier modes, such as rail and IWT. The cornerstone of synchromodality lies on real time decision making and planning, utilizing advanced digital technologies and data availability.

European freight transport network has a long way ahead to succeed environmental targets in a cost-effective way. Moreover, road freight seems to suffer of severe congestion and fragmentation, leading to unsustainable supply chains. Rail is constantly upgrading, but there is still a lot to be done in terms of promoting IWT. Except for the main river corridors (Rhine and Danube) that serve industrial areas of the Central/North Europe, there are many navigable rivers, tributaries and canals that have potential capacity

to absorb a high portion of freight transport. Yet, issues such as navigability disruptions, infrastructure failures, and policy regulations remain substantial barriers to develop IWT.

Synchromodality principles, as presented in the current chapter, can contribute to the development of a robust European transport corridor network that will incorporate IWW in a more holistic way, to create sustainable supply chains. The CRISTAL Synchromodal Corridor Management System, which is described in the next chapter, considers the aforementioned principles and requirements, in order to develop a platform that will demonstrate through dedicated pilots the significance of synchromodal services and IWT. The expected impacts of SCMS will serve in the future as a facilitator to confront the obstacles of implementing synchromodality and increase IWT share (Table 7).

Table 7 Principles of synchromodality and SCMS role and requirements

Synchromodality	CRISTAL SCMS impact and expected contribution	Key objectives
Modal variation (modal shift, i.e., rail, IWT)	Demonstrate effectiveness of non-core IWW corridors	Supply chain efficiency
Real time planning	Develop a platform to aggregate data from other information system providers and sensors' monitoring	Transport network reliability
Reduced emissions	Demonstrate CO ₂ reduction using IWT in contrast to alternative routes including road/rail	Sustainability
Information sharing	Disseminate information collected in CRISTAL partners to all supply chain stakeholders	Standardization
Single point of service	CRISTAL platform	Standardization
Capacity utilization	Provide the necessary information gathered from external systems concerning the capacity of others modes of transport	Supply chain efficiency

The above discussion and table define the scope and the objectives of the SCMS of CRISTAL which is further defined and adapted to the resilient and efficient Inland Waterways scope in the next chapter.

3. CRISTAL approach on the Sychromodal Corridor Management System for Inland Waterways resilience and efficiency

3.1 SCMS main specifications and objectives

In this chapter, the specifications and goals of a Sychromodal Corridor Management System (SCMS) development for Inland Waterway Corridors are presented. In this context, a comprehensive understanding of the system users and involved actors' roles, system essential components, main functionalities, possible services, advantages, and potential difficulties for implementation and operation are discussed. As mentioned in the previous section, sychromodal freight transportation enhances intermodal and co-modal transport by coordinating across multiple transportation modes in real-time, leading to increased efficiency, reduced costs, and a lower environmental impact. In CRISTAL the SCMS aims at connecting the ecosystem that manages, exploits or uses a river corridor for securing non-disruption, efficiency and sustainability of river-based transport & logistics operations. This will be achieved though real time monitoring, timely information sharing, criticalities assessment and collaborative planning to efficiently respond to uncertainties.

Exploring the Sychromodal Corridor Management System: Characteristics, Requirements and Challenges

The development and implementation of an SCMS is contingent on several critical factors, including access to relevant data and information sources, the ability to switch between transportation modes along the corridor in short term, the commitment to optimal utilization of corridor resources, and level of collaboration among stakeholders, such as shippers, carriers, logistics service providers, and infrastructure operators [41].

The SCMS strives to enhance transportation operations through real-time information, dynamic planning, and optimal resource utilization. Its primary objective is to make transportation more efficient, cost-effective, and seamless by considering the needs of multiple commodities and stakeholders [46].

Optimization is at the core of the SCMS. The SCMS plans to reduce transportation costs and emissions, and increases efficiency by optimizing the utilization of resources, such as transportation vehicles and infrastructure. The real-time optimization and network service design aspect of the system continuously monitors and optimizes transportation operations using real-time data and information from the network. The planning horizon also plays a crucial role in the system's tactical and operational decisions by balancing short-term and long-term goals and priorities. This dynamic transportation planning allows for quick and effective planning in response to unexpected shipments, utilizing real-time data and network information. The capacitated transportation network component models the optimal distribution of capacity between different transportation modes and vehicles [45].

The concept of sychromodality has been described with varying features and specifications in different scientific sources. These features can influence the design and implementation of a SCMS. Table 8, based

on [43] and [41] outlines the key features of synchronomodality and explain the impact of each of these features on the design and implementation of the SCMS.

Table 8 Assessment of Characteristics and Requirements of the synchronomodality and their possible influence on Synchronodal Corridor Management System

Synchronomodality Characteristics/Requirements	Influence on SCMS
Real-time switching between transportation modes	Dynamic switching between modes based on real-time traffic, network conditions, and other relevant factors
Optimal utilization of multimodal transport network resources	Optimize utilization of resources, including transport vehicles and infrastructure, to minimize costs and maximize efficiency
Cooperation between transport actors	Facilitate cooperation between transport actors, such as shippers, carriers, logistics service providers, and infrastructure operators, for seamless and coordinated transportation operations
Real-time optimization and network service design	Continuously monitor and optimize transportation operations in real-time, using data and information from the network
Tactical and operational decisions influenced by planning horizon	Use planning horizon to make tactical and operational decisions that balance short-term and long-term goals and priorities
Dynamic transportation planning	Quickly and effectively plan for unforeseen shipments, using real-time data and network information
Capacitated transport network	Model optimal distribution of capacity between different transportation modes and vehicles
Multi-commodity and multi-stakeholder	Take into consideration the needs and requirements of multiple commodities and multiple stakeholders
Real-time network information, transparency, and data exchange	Use real-time network information and data exchange to improve decision-making and optimize transportation operations

The following parts of this section aim to delve into the definition of the inland waterways-based Synchronodal Corridor within the context of SCMS. The discussions will also touch upon the various challenges that need to be overcome in order to meet the established objective criteria.

Defining the Corridor

A corridor in synchromodality is defined as a set of interconnected transport services that link origins, destinations, and intermodal terminals, also referred to as transshipment points [42]. The corridor will be modelled as a multi-directional graph, where nodes represent origin and destination points and edges represent the transport services connecting them. Unlike traditional graphs that display a single connection between nodes, this graph can have multiple connections between nodes.

Figure 14 Illustration of a corridor represented as a connected graph, with each point representing a port of entry/exit for cargo and the edges, possibly multiple, indicating the means of transportation between the ports.

Each transport service has unique characteristics, including its schedule, available container slot capacity, mode of transportation, and type of vehicle. The type of vehicle is crucial in determining the environmental impact and cost of the service, for example, the difference between diesel and electric trains [41]. The duration and distance of the services can be static or dynamic variables. They can be calculated following the schedules for barge and train services, or the average transport velocity for truck in different times of the day, or any other intervals. These values can be updated as required. Transshipment points are also defined by their location, duration, cost, and environmental impact per container unit.

This modelled corridor is the foundation for the development of the SCMS, which aims to optimize the utilization of transport services especially inland water way transports, by balancing demand and supply of containers and considering the environmental impact and cost of each service. The system should employ mathematical algorithms and decision-making tools to identify the most efficient transport routes

while considering the characteristics of each transport service, the type of vehicle used, and the availability of container slots.

Before implementing the SCMS, it's crucial to assess the potential challenges to better understand the desired outcome and what can be achieved. In the next step, we will explain the various challenges that need to be addressed for the effective implementation and widespread adoption of the SCMS. Despite its potential benefits, there are several technical, operational, and institutional obstacles that must be overcome. These challenges span from data collection and management, over the integration of different transport modes and stakeholders, to the creation of incentives for the use of the system. By addressing these challenges, it is possible to establish a more sustainable and efficient intermodal transport system that benefits both the environment and the economy.

SCMS Challenges

SCMS encounters various challenges in ensuring the efficient functioning of the synchromodal transportation network. This list of challenges is not exhaustive and may be subject to change based on further research. However, by reviewing [44], [15] and [41] as well as conducting a brief consultation with relevant experts, the following challenges have been identified as significant considerations for the SCMS. We also categorize these challenges to provide a more straightforward and transparent explanation. These challenges include:

I. Operations and Infrastructure Challenges

1. **Maintenance and Upkeep of Infrastructure:** The maintenance and upkeep of the infrastructure along the synchromodal corridor, including waterway, rail, and road components, is crucial for the smooth operation of the network. The system must consider the costs and schedules for maintenance and upkeep.
2. **Port Capacity and Operations:** The ports along the synchromodal corridor are crucial for the transfer of containers and must have adequate capacity and efficient operations to handle the transshipment.
3. **Parking and Storage:** Adequate parking and storage spaces for containers are becoming a challenge with increasing demand for transport services. The synchromodal corridor management system must consider their availability for smooth operation.
4. **Dependency on Water Level:** The waterway component of the synchromodal network heavily relies on the water level, which affects its navigability and capacity. This makes the maintenance and monitoring of water levels crucial for the smooth operation of the network.

II. Environmental Challenges

5. **Environmental Emissions:** The transportation sector contributes significantly to carbon emissions and the synchromodal corridor management system must minimize the carbon footprint and reduce the impact on the environment.

III. Stakeholder Challenges

6. Stakeholder Trust: To ensure sustainability of the synchromodal transport network, the system must increase the trust of stakeholders in the waterway as a reliable mode of transport. This can be achieved by enabling real-time decision making and maintaining the infrastructure.

IV. Intermodal Transport Services Challenges

7. Intermodal Transport Services: The system must consider various intermodal transport services, such as barge, rail, and truck, and their respective costs, capacities, and schedules.
8. Transshipment: The system must consider the limitations and costs of transshipment at the start or end of a service, based on cargo weight.
9. Fixed vs. Flexible Schedules: Barge and rail services might have fixed schedules, but truck services have time-flexible departures and arrivals.
10. Transport Duration: The duration of each mode of transport must be accurately calculated and considered. This can depend on many factors like weather, time and date of travel etc.
11. Limited Capacity: The capacities of each mode of transport are limited and the system sometimes must provide the flexibility to set extra capacity for selected services.
12. Fleet Management: The system cannot easily focus on managing a multiple vehicle fleet as each transport service might have a different type of vehicle with different characteristics and requirements.

V. Customer Orders and Demand Challenges

13. Customer Orders: The system must consider the origin, destination, time window, transport interval, and number of TEUs (Twenty-foot Equivalent Unit) for each customer order.
14. Network Demand and Free Capacity: The system must use customer transportation demand as input to determine the total network demand and free capacity of all services.

VI. Optimization Challenges

15. Optimal Routing and Service Selection: The system has to assign customer orders efficiently and find the optimal routing and service selection using the free transport capacity.
16. Optimization Objectives: The system might have to consider multiple optimization objectives, including minimizing monetary costs, reducing transport environmental impact, and increasing utilization of transport network resources.
17. Deterministic and Stochastic Values: The system might have to consider both deterministic and stochastic values for transport demand and travel time.

18. Flexible Transport Services: The system must enable the routing of single loading units and consider different modes of transport for each unit. Therefore, a big set of conditions should be considered.

Description of the main goals and objectives of the system

It is recognised that CRISTAL cannot address all the above presented challenges in the context of the SCMS development. The goal is to define the architecture and develop the platform connectivity infrastructure & services that will fulfil the pilots needs and will showcase at the pilot's ecosystems the validity and the usefulness of the SCMS in full collaboration with the other existing systems.

In this context we define the broad system goals and functionalities of the SCMS to drive the system design, given the available information on multimodal transportation, advancements in logistics, and the constantly evolving landscape of information in the field. Thus, while the system is specified to effectively model and attain the general objectives and functionalities it will also be possible in the next phase of the project to classify the detailed requirements of the SCMS services through further detailed specifications with the project pilots and stakeholders.

The first step towards achieving the SCMS objectives is to build trust among stakeholders in the River Transport & logistics industry. This can be accomplished by showcasing the efficiency of waterways by creating/supporting (through the SCMS) comprehensive planning with efficient optimization methods, detailed plans that address discrepancies recovery and mitigation, to secure an optimal efficient flow of goods which will reduce financial losses and optimize resources. The SCMS objectives are summarized in Table 9 Further explanation of these objectives is provided as follow:

1. Increasing the usage of the waterways:

This objective aims to promote the usage of the waterways as a reliable mode of transportation for various stakeholders such as freight and passenger transport. This can be achieved by improving the monitoring of the navigability and infrastructures and services along the waterway, making it a more convenient option for transport and reducing the operational obstacles.

2. Emission consideration in planning:

With an increasing focus on reducing greenhouse gas emissions, it is important to consider the emissions generated in the corridor in the transport planning and decision-making process. This includes assessing the emissions from vessels and other sources along the corridor and implementing measures to reduce these emissions.

3. Monitoring Intermodal Transport Services:

One of the goals can be monitoring the cost, capacity, and schedules of the transport services provided by barge, rail, and trucks in the corridor. This includes keeping track of the schedules of barge and rail services, and the flexible departures and arrivals of truck services. The duration of each service will be based on the schedules, as well as the distance and average velocity of multimodal transport services. The system will also monitor the network demand and free capacity of all services.

4. Planning for transshipment and customer orders:

This objective involves planning the transshipment of containers at nodes, considering transshipment costs based on the type of cargo. The system will also plan for customer orders defined by origin, destination, time window, and number of TEUs to be transported. The system can provide time flexibility to customers by allowing them to select a latest time of arrival. Orders will be assigned within a short period of time using the free transport capacity, and the optimal combination of transport services will be chosen within the customer's time window, allowing for earlier arrivals at the destination, focusing on the usage of the water way. The system can also simulate possible savings and resource efficiency improvements by enabling more service capacity or a larger transport time window using the flexibility options [41].

5. Information/Message Centre:

The system can provide a central platform for information and messaging for customers and stakeholders. This can include real-time updates on transport services, pricing, and schedules, as well as information on safety measures and other relevant information. This centre can be accessible through a user-friendly interface, making it easy for stakeholders to access the information they need.

6. Data provision for informed decision-making:

The SCMS can facilitate better cooperation between stakeholders and improve transparency by providing accurate and relevant data for informed decision-making. The system will also provide data for further research and analysis in order to continually improve the synchromodal transport network.

Table 9 Highlighting the purpose of each goal of SCMS and how it contributes to the overall success of the SCMS system.

Goal/Objective	Description
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increasing usage of waterways 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote usage of waterways as a reliable mode of transport by improving navigability (through better monitoring, infrastructure and services)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Emission consideration in planning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consider emissions in decision-making and implement measures to reduce emissions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monitoring intermodal transport services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monitor cost, capacity, and schedules of transport services in the corridor
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Planning for transshipment and customer orders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Plan transshipment and fulfil customer orders within a flexible time window
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information/Message Centre 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide a central platform for information and messaging for stakeholders

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data provision for informed decision-making 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitate cooperation and improve transparency by providing accurate data for informed decision-making
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3.2 Identification of SCMS main stakeholders

The main stakeholders of the Synchronodal Corridor Management System are important to the process of defining the system specifications since they constitute the “contributors” and the “consumers” of the produced benefit by the system. In this section the definition of the SCMS stakeholders is approached through a general overview of Supply Chain stakeholders followed by an identification of the key stakeholders in the European Inland Waterway system, (based on the work undertaken in WP4 and reported in D4.1) and finally, a selection from the list of the key stakeholders in the European Inland Waterway system is made to define the core of stakeholders of the SCMS based on their expected level of interaction with the system.

General Supply Chain stakeholders

In Figure 15 a general overview of a supply chain is given. From this figure can be observed that there are multiple layers to the supply chain. These layers are the logistics layer, the transaction layer and the governance layer.

Figure 15 Supply chain structure [49]

For the scope of the CRISTAL project the main focus is on the hinterland part of the transport chain. This part starts (or ends) at a deep-sea port and has a final destination (or origin) in a warehouse in the hinterland. In this process there are a lot of actors involved ranging from actors who execute the logistics layer (deep-sea terminal operators, inland carriers, inland terminal operators and finally the consignee (or consignor). On top of that a lot of “transaction” actors are linked to these operations. These actors are forwarders or logistics service providers, insurance companies, depots (for empty containers) and banks (for financing the transport functions). From a governance point of view, we need to consider the port authorities, the hinterland infrastructure providers, customs and inspection authorities and governments.

It needs to be determined which actor is responsible for which part of transport chain and which actors takes which risk (incoterms), letter of credit (to pay for goods by the receiver) and an (inland) Bill of Lading (B/L) when the transport is executed. This inland B/L is a document in which the captain of a vessel (or driver of a truck) declares to have taken the goods listed on the document aboard and undertakes to transport the goods to the named destination and to deliver to a designated person. This inland B/L might need to change (or needs an update) in case the cargo switches from transport mode due to a proposed change by the SCMS.

Main stakeholders of the European Inland Waterway system

This section will provide a summary of the main stakeholders identified in WP4 (see Table 10). There are many different definitions and approaches for ‘a stakeholder’. The classic approach, according to the current literature, states the following: “a stakeholder is any group or individual who can affect or is affected by the achievement of the organization’s objectives” [47]. When wanting to identify key stakeholders in the European Inland Waterway system, many different approaches can be applied. In the context of deliverable 4.1, the following key stakeholders were identified, using the framework of [50] and the input of the project’s pilot partners itself.

Table 10 Summary of main stakeholders of the European inland waterway system

Main stakeholders/actors	Detailed stakeholders/actors	Examples ¹
Infrastructure managers	Rail, road, IWT, ...	VNF, AIPo, SNCF, SAPN, ...
Transport companies	Shipping lines, trucks, rail freight operators, barge operators, ...	CFT, Coalis, Transports Lalemant, SNCF, Mauffrey, ...
Inland ports	Terminal operators, ...	Haropa, ...
Deep-sea ports connected to rivers	Terminal operators, port authorities, ...	Haropa, ...
Logistics service providers	1PL, 2PL, 3PL, 4PL and 5PL	HGK, Haeger&Schmidt, MAFF, Transest, ...

¹ The summary above only gives French examples because as of this moment, only the French pilot provided input for deliverable 4.1.

Shipper/cargo owner	Sender and receiver	-
Technology providers and digital service providers	Suppliers and partners	UNEW, CERTH, Fraunhofer
Regulators of IWT	EU, federal government, local government, ...	Ministères chargés de l'économie, du budget, des transports, ... Communauté Urbaine, CIM, ...
People	Citizens, environmental groups, interest groups, ...	
Private companies	Farmer associations, power plants, tourism sector, ...	Syndicat des énergies renouvelables, Union des Entreprises de Transport et de Logistique de France, ...
Neutral Partners and knowledge creation partners for enabling data collection and analysis and for supporting collaboration	Universities, ...	CERTH, University of Antwerp, Fraunhofer, ...

Infrastructure managers, such as VNF (in the French pilot case) or AIPo (in the Italian pilot case), mainly manage the infrastructure and oversee the inland waterways in certain regions. Depending on the country or region, there is a difference in the tasks and jobs of the infrastructure manager. Additionally, infrastructure managers also exist for other transportation modes such as rail and road. Because of their importance in the network, these stakeholders are identified as key stakeholders. Next, transport companies are identified. These companies vary greatly and cover companies from shipping lines and barge operators to rail freight operators and truck companies. Thirdly, inland ports are brought up as key stakeholders where terminal operators and other actors work that have a direct link with IWT. The deep-sea ports cannot be excluded from this list. These ports have terminal operators and port authorities among other stakeholders that have a significant role. Next, logistics service providers exist in many forms. From 1PL, where the producer delivers the cargo to the client with their own truck, vessel or other transportation mode, to 5PL, where the supply chain and logistics get outsourced to an external provider which has no own assets and looks at the network, rather than the chain. After this, the shipper or cargo owner is mentioned. Here, a distinction needs to be made between the senders and the receivers of cargo. Both parties are key actors in the framework. Then, a key stakeholder was added through input received from the French pilot. They added technology providers. This stakeholder is linked with the project partners of CRISTAL designing technologies for the improvement of the waterways.

It is of great importance that the regulatory side of transport is not forgotten. Therefore, regulators of IWT, such as the European Union, federal governments and local governments are included in the framework. In addition, people surrounding the waterways have to be part of the framework. These

people can be citizens living near a waterway or environmental and interest groups. Next, private companies in the chain, network or surroundings need to be considered. From farmer associations to power plants and the tourism sector, those companies need to be implemented and integrated in the framework as key stakeholders. Lastly, universities and other knowledge institutions, such as the University of Antwerp, are integrated because of their work on the CRISTAL project itself [51].

Main stakeholders of SCMS

Based on the literature review of chapter 2 regarding the complexity of freight transport systems and the relationships between main actors (Figure 3) together with the Corridor Management Systems objectives and functionalities and key stakeholders that are involved in multimodal/synchromodal transportation (Figure 8), it becomes clear that the majority of the main stakeholders identified for the European Inland Waterway transport system and presented in Table 10 can also be considered as stakeholders of the SCMS.

More specifically, considering as key stakeholders the main core of actors that directly affect or are affected by the operation of the SCMS following the definition used above [47], then the list of main stakeholders of SCMS includes those who:

- plan and execute the transportation activities (Logistics service providers, transport companies),
- provide & maintain the infrastructure for realising the movement of cargo (infrastructure managers of all modes, inland/deep-sea ports),
- are responsible for the development, operation and feeding of the SCMS with the required data to operate (technology providers),
- create the legal framework for the IWT and are also interested in the monitoring of the system performance for supporting decision and policy-making (authorities, e.g., central/federal government, local administrations).

This identification of the key stakeholders of SCMS is confirmed also to a large extent from the information received from the pilots and is presented in the next section, through their feedback regarding their view on the stakeholders expected to benefit from the SCMS system.

3.3 Stakeholder views and needs, definition of IWT critical processes

As in any case of an IT system development which aims at enhancing or expanding the operations of an already existing transportation system, an integral part of this process is the interaction with the actors that will use and benefit from the proposed system. In this way the developers will ensure that the system under development answers to actual needs of the potential users and that they understand its value proposition. At the same time, they can utilise their feedback in order to define and refine specific services and solutions that are important for the system operation.

In this context, it was decided to conduct a short questionnaire survey in order to collect information regarding the current methods of handling disruptions in the project pilot sites that will support the development of the Synchromodal Corridor Management System. The project has three pilots in which the (IWW) transportation systems are currently at different stages of maturity and operation, having different governance structures and systems deployed and therefore different needs and requirements.

CRISTAL aspires to develop a SCMS that will be able to answer to needs of all types of IWT systems and for this reason the information provided from the three pilot sites is a valuable input for the SCMS development that will be realised in the next period of the project. Finally, it should be noted that the survey aimed at compiling an initial view of the current status regarding the disruption handling in the three pilot sites. The detailed mapping of all processes within IWWs including the disruptions handling is an activity that will be undertaken in WP6 and will also feed the development of the SCMS.

Unlike the questionnaire developed in the context of WP1 which was addressed mainly to the infrastructure operators and infrastructure maintenance issues of the pilot sites, this questionnaire was focused on the logistics operations side of the IWW and therefore its questions are mostly related to issues, choices and decisions that consider mainly the stakeholders who plan and perform the actual transportation of cargo in the IWW systems. The pilot leaders were selected to provide their answer despite not being directly involved to the logistics operations because of having an overall knowledge and view of the IWW system structure and operations in their sites while being in close day to day contact and collaboration with the relevant (logistics) stakeholders, receiving their views and feedback.

The structure of the Questionnaire was based on five main questions/sections. In the first section, the aim was to map the current processes related to the handling of disruptions in IWW operations, starting from the transmission of the relevant information until the decision for action and the influencing parameters. In the second part, the aim was to identify and assess the main problems of transport operators emerging due to disruptions. In the third part, the aim was to collect the views of stakeholders regarding the benefits of a Synchromodal Corridor Management System along with their opinion regarding the main types of stakeholders that could benefit from this system and the appropriate entity for managing it. Finally, in the last two sections, the participants were asked to express their thoughts about additional services that could be added to the SCMS and any other type of information that they believed that will be useful for the SCMS development. The questionnaire can be found in the Annex I of the present document.

Questionnaire results

With respect to the first section of the questionnaire and the dissemination of information to stakeholders regarding disruptions in IWW operations, in the cases of the Polish and French pilots this information is mainly transmitted to the skippers through the official channels and not in other categories of stakeholders (e.g., LSPs) who would probably be interested to have it, at least not directly. In the Italian pilot however, this information is transmitted besides the skippers also to a list of other stakeholders and to regional offices responsible for the supervision of inland navigation in cases of serious disruptions. These offices then decide and send an order for stopping navigation. Moreover, depending on the pilot case this information is transmitted at different speeds. More specifically, in the French pilot where EURIS system is available, the information about disruptions is transmitted immediately through notices to skippers from the VNF territorial management. The same applies to the Italian pilot, where the information is transmitted immediately via radio to skippers that are using the infrastructure and through an email to other stakeholders. On the other hand, in the Polish pilots, skippers need to visit the websites of IWW infrastructure manager to get this information and in some cases the updates are delayed thus requiring direct communication through phones in order to be timely informed.

As for the actions selected by the transport operators when a disruption occurs, both in the French and Italian pilots, there are some cases when the transport operators chose to move to another mode of transport while in other, they chose to wait for the disruption to end and the operations to resume. It should be noted that in the first case the most usual alternative option is road transport. An interesting finding that is coming from the Polish pilot is that once the cargo is loaded to barges and the transport starts, it is very rare to switch to another mode, mainly because of lack of interfaces to other modes along the route where transshipment can take place. However, if the disruption is known ahead then usually another mode is selected instead of waiting.

Regarding the parameters that are affecting the decisions to act in cases of disruption, the answers revealed an alignment to a large extent among the pilot sites. The type of cargo, the estimation of the duration of the disruption, the expected additional cost of the transshipment and the availability of the alternative modes of transport are common parameters among all pilots while in the French pilot possible contractual obligations and legal issues that may hinder modal shift is also considered.

Moving on to the second part of the questionnaire which focused on the main problems that transport operators are facing when a disruption occurs, it is a common finding among all three pilots that disruptions cause significant increase in the cost of operations. In the case of the French and Italian pilots, the decrease of reliability towards the customers appears to be also an important issue. At the same time, it is considered by all pilots that there are no actual alternatives available because of the lack of efficient interfaces to other modes of transport and also there is not enough visibility of the alternative options. In addition, the Italian and Polish pilot consider the type of cargo transported in their sites and the additional cost required for the transshipment as deterrent factors for modal shift. Finally, the Polish pilot considers the transmission of relevant information slow for supporting timely decisions. The latter is very important when combined with a comment provided which states that the Polish pilot rivers suffer from limited number of transport nodes (ports) to shift the cargo to other modes.

In the third part of the questionnaire, the view of stakeholders was collected regarding the expected impact of the implementation of a Synchronodal Corridor Management System to their operations. The SCMS was described as a system that is planned to provide the following services:

1. Produce early alerts of disruptions & notify the relevant stakeholders of IWT systems
2. Estimate the impact on operations of the identified disruptions
3. Proposition of alternatives to the IWW stakeholders to address the impacts of these disruptions including a possible mode change (concept of synchronodality)
4. Support the decisions of stakeholders through a toolbox of services (e.g., rerouting tools, visibility services etc.)

Based on this description, all pilots estimated that SCMS has the potential to significantly contribute in a better visibility of the alternative choices that exist in the case of disruption and that it will also have a positive impact in reducing the cost of disruptions. In addition, the French and Italian pilots believe that it can facilitate the connection to other modes. On the other hand, the Polish pilot expects a significant improvement in the reliability of the IWT system and also to the planning under uncertainty and timely notification of the disruptions.

With respect to the stakeholders that could benefit from being part of the SCMS ecosystem, it appears that there is an agreement among the project pilots that shippers and freight forwarders will mainly benefit from the SCMS as was expected while it is also considered that public authorities and infrastructure managers will also be able to make better use of their assets.

Finally, all pilots consider in general that the management of the SCMS should be made by the infrastructure managers. In the cases of the Italian and Polish pilots the IWW infrastructure manager are considered more appropriate while the French pilot considers that all transport modes should lead the governance scheme through a company partly or fully publicly owned. Moreover, the Polish pilot suggested the funding of its operation to be included in the fees for the use of infrastructure.

Conclusions on the stakeholders' views and needs

Analysing the answers provided by the pilot sites, the following main conclusions are drawn:

- In some of the pilot cases, there is a gap today regarding the direct dissemination of information related to disruptions (early alerts) to a wider range of stakeholders of the IWT systems besides the skippers. In the case of the Polish pilot, there is also a need for more timely transmission of this information.
- There are some parameters affecting the decisions for responding to disruptions that appear to be significant and should be supported in order for stakeholders to take better informed decisions. These parameters include the estimated durations of the disruption, the estimated cost of transshipment to other modes and the availability of other modes of transport.
- The visibility of the infrastructure (location and technical characteristics) for all modes of transport is considered very important for handling disruptions.
- There is also a requirement for better connection of IWW to the other modes of transport, especially rail. Two of the three pilots requested, through suggestions for additional services, better cooperation among the three modes and real time visibility of capacities availability, tariffs and schedules as well as of the contact points that could take the form of an official partnership.
- The concept of synchromodality is considered as a driver that can provide solution to the high cost for operators due to disruptions while in some cases together with the early detection systems it can support operational decisions and the planning of transportation under uncertainty.

All the conclusions and requirements described above provide a guidance for defining in the following section the main components and services that will be part of the Synchromodal Corridor Management System in order to provide solutions to some of these identified needs of the users. However, the final selection of the components and services that will be included in the SCMS will also consider the limitations and available capabilities of the project which are also presented in the next section.

3.4 Selection of the SCMS components & services: technical specifications, standards and connectors

Components and Services of the Synchronodal Corridor Management System (SCMS)

To ensure the optimal operation of the SCMS, it is crucial to select the appropriate components and services based on the objectives outlined in section 3.1. This can be achieved through a series of steps, including a workshop with stakeholders, market analysis and literature review, identification of potential solutions, and evaluation of solutions.

Market Analysis and Literature Review

The market analysis is the first step in selecting the appropriate components and services for the SCMS. The analysis provides an overview of the current solutions and services available in the market, including the strengths and weaknesses of each solution. Table 11 below provides a list of key elements, tools, services, and components that are suggested for performing a good Synchronodal Corridor Management System. These components are essential for managing the transportation network in a highly optimized and efficient manner [42].

Table 11 Essential components for managing the synchronodal transportation network

Key Element	Suggested Tools/Services/Components	Reference
ETA and Transit Time Optimization Tools	Re-routing or switching to another transportation mode based on real-time information	[66], [70], [57]
Capacity Optimization Tools	Allocating freight to two parallel transportation modes, intermodal rail and road	[56], [62]
Predictive Analytics Tools	Using an estimate of future values for transportation demand and traffic conditions	[63]
Real-Time Monitoring Tools	Re-optimizing based on real-time data about deviating events	[57]
Cost Optimization Tools	Minimizing supply chain costs	[56], [62]
Early Decision and Information Tools	Reacting to disturbances on transportation services and evaluating potential re-routing	[70], [57]
Terminal Optimization Tools	Switching transportation modes at intermediate terminals	[62]

In addition to the table above, a survey on synchromodal transportation conducted in the case of Rotterdam [67] investigated the experiences and obstacles faced by companies involved in hinterland connections of the Port of Rotterdam. 30 companies were surveyed and the findings were analysed based on the framework of critical factors on synchromodality by [68]. These critical factors are also explained in Chapter 2 of this report. The companies that had experience with synchromodality mentioned the factors that obstruct synchromodal transport. These factors can help the SCMS to adapt which services to fulfil their needs. Table 12 below shows the main obstructions mentioned by the experienced companies.

Table 12 Main obstructions by companies involved in hinterland connections of the Port of Rotterdam

Obstructions	Description	Example
Infrastructure	Availability of services and infrastructure is not efficiently organized	Inland shipping vessels having to deliver containers at various terminals in one port, leading to inefficient utilization of resources
Inflexible Product	Product has specific requirements that may not be compatible with all modes of transport	Product requires temperature control, limiting the options for synchromodal transport
Customer Requirements	Customer preferences limit options for synchromodal transport	Customer preferences for specific delivery dates or modes of transport

Identification of Potential Solutions

The next step in the selection process is to identify potential solutions based on the objectives and requirements outlined in section 3.1. This can include solutions specifically designed for synchromodal transportation and solutions that can be adapted to meet the specific requirements of the SCMS. The solutions should be evaluated based on their ability to meet the objectives and requirements of the system, their compatibility with existing systems, and their overall cost-effectiveness. In the next part, we discuss these components.

Figure 16 The main suggested components of the SCMS to fulfil the objectives defined in section 3.1

Components for Effective SCMS Operation:

1. **Decision-making Core:** The Decision-making Core is a critical component of the SCMS as it provides the necessary information and support for optimizing the synchronomodality of the transportation network. This component should provide optimization tools for decision-makers to make informed decisions and achieve the objectives of the system, such as reducing emissions, minimizing transit time, or reducing transportation cost. The main tools include:
 - **Route Optimization Tools:** These tools help decision-makers to determine the optimal route for transportation of goods, taking into consideration transit time, cost, emissions, and available capacity of different modes of transportation.
 1. **Emission Optimization Tools:** These tools help decision-makers to evaluate the emissions generated by different modes of transportation, identify the sources of emissions, and implement measures to reduce these emissions, ensuring the most environmentally-friendly transportation mode is selected and reducing the carbon footprint of the transportation network.
 2. **Cost Optimization Tools:** These tools provide decision-makers with information to minimize transportation cost while ensuring goods are delivered on time by evaluating costs associated with different modes of transportation, including fuel costs, labour costs, and maintenance costs.
 3. **ETA and Transit Time Optimization Tools:** These tools assist decision-makers in determining the optimal route for the transportation of goods by considering several factors such as estimated time of arrival (ETA), transit time, cost, and capacity of

different modes of transportation. The tools analyse these parameters and provide recommendations for the quickest and most efficient route that minimizes transportation time and cost while maximizing capacity utilization.

Figure 17 The components of the decision-making core

- **Capacity Optimization Tools:** These tools provide decision-makers with information on the available capacity of different modes of transportation and enable them to optimize utilization, reducing transit time and minimizing transportation cost by considering demand for transportation and available capacity. **Terminal Optimization Tools:** These tools help decision-makers to optimize the utilization of terminals, including transshipment terminals, warehousing facilities, and loading docks, reducing transit time and minimizing transportation cost by considering demand for transshipment, available capacity, and cost of transshipment.

The optimization tools in the decision-making core requires precise decision-making. The decision model must be quantitative and the field of operations research can help improve decision-making efficiency in the SCMS through the use of scientific methods such as linear programming, mixed integer programming, nonlinear programming, and meta-heuristics like evolutionary algorithms and heuristic search methods [41].

2. **Monitoring and Observatory Core:** The Monitoring and Observatory Core is an essential component of the SCMS and is responsible for monitoring the system's performance in real-time. This component enables the continuous collection, processing, and analysis of data, providing decision-makers with valuable insights and information to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of the system.

The Monitoring and Observatory Core includes a variety of tools and services for real-time tracking of the transportation network, such as GPS tracking, real-time data analysis, and performance monitoring. It also provides an overview of key performance indicators, including transit time, cost, and emissions. The core

includes user-friendly visualization tools, such as maps and dashboards, for analysing system performance and quickly identifying trends and patterns in the data.

Some of the crucial sub-tools of the Monitoring and Observatory Core are:

- **Real-Time Monitoring Tools:** These tools provide real-time monitoring and tracking of the transportation network, giving decision-makers a clear and accurate view of the current state of the network. The tool uses data from GPS tracking devices, sensors, and other sources to provide real-time updates on the location, speed, and status of transportation units.
 - **Performance Metrics Tools:** These tools provide key performance metrics for the transportation network, such as transit time, delivery time, transportation cost, and emissions. Decision-makers have the necessary information to make informed decisions and optimize the performance of the network.
 - **Integrated Dashboard Tools:** These tools provide a centralized and integrated dashboard for decision-makers to access and analyse data from various sources. The dashboard provides a clear and concise view of the network's performance, enabling quick identification of areas for improvement and informed decisions.
 - **Predictive Analytics Tools:** These tools use machine learning and predictive analytics algorithms to provide forecasts and predictions on the future performance of the network. Decision-makers can anticipate and prepare for potential disruptions and optimize the performance of the network proactively.
 - **Impact Identification Tools:** The Impact Identification Services offered by SCMS can be designed to identify the impact of various events and changes on the transport network, including traffic congestion, changes in transport schedules, and unexpected events such as natural disasters or road closures. These services might provide relevant data and visualizations, allowing stakeholders to quickly identify and mitigate the impact of these events. This information might be critical for ensuring the synchromodal transport network remains adaptable and responsive to changes in the market, reducing the risk of unexpected disruptions.
 - **Early Decision and Information Tools:** The Early Decision and Information Services offered by SCMS might provide stakeholders with real-time information and updates on transport services, schedules, and pricing. This information can be crucial for decision-making and might enable stakeholders to take advantage of new opportunities and reduce operational costs. The information can be provided through a user-friendly interface that is accessible to all stakeholders, including customers, transport providers, and regulators. The information services also might include real-time monitoring of transport capacity, which can be critical for ensuring optimal utilization of resources and reducing the danger of financial losses.
3. **The Data processing and Information Hub** of SCMS is a comprehensive platform that gathers external data and provides stakeholders with valuable insights and real-time information to support informed decisions regarding the synchromodal transport network. The hub includes the following components:

- **Data Exchange tools:** These tools are designed to enhance cooperation between stakeholders and ensure effective data sharing. The services enable stakeholders to share information and data on transport services, capacity, and pricing, reducing the risk of misunderstandings and increasing transparency. The data exchange services also provide stakeholders with access to a wide range of data sources, including government and industry databases, to support informed decision-making based on accurate information.
- **Data processing and Information tools:** These tools offer stakeholders a comprehensive set of tools and data to support informed decision-making about the synchromodal transport network. The services provide access to various data sources, such as government and industry databases, allowing stakeholders to base their decisions on accurate information. The tools collect, process, and analyse data from various sources, providing insights into the performance of the transportation network. Decision-makers can identify trends, patterns, and anomalies in transportation data to gain valuable insights into the efficiency and effectiveness of the network.

Selection of the SCMS Components & Services in CRISTAL

The selection of components and services for the SCMS in CRISTAL must be done with care and consideration for several key factors. These factors include the needs and requirements of the synchromodal corridor, the availability and the volume of data and transactions that the system must handle, scalability to accommodate future growth, and the availability of technical support and maintenance services to ensure the system operates smoothly.

A typical SCMS would include services such as real-time tracking and monitoring of shipments, route planning and optimization, data analytics and reporting, and automated dispatch and scheduling. These services should provide a comprehensive and integrated solution for managing and optimizing the flow of goods and resources along the synchromodal corridor, as described in [65]. The SCMS may also include additional components and services, such as observatory services as already explained, depending on the specific needs of CRISTAL.

The selection of the final components and services for CRISTAL must consider the availability of data and be synchronized with other work packages that will provide data to the SCMS. The selection process must also consider the kind of data that is available and needed by the services to ensure they provide the desired outcomes. Further steps in the service selection procedure will be described in detail in the next sections.

Available data in CRISTAL

The focus of the information available in CRISTAL is on providing data and monitoring the navigability and maintenance conditions of Pilot rivers in Poland, Italy, and France. The possible internal data for these three Pilots may include information about the navigability of the waterways, which can be forecasted based on monitoring various parameters such as water depth, river current conditions (temperature, speed, and direction), meteorological measurements (air temperature, pressure, wind speed, and direction), and sonar measurements of river depth. The data is acquired using different sensors, an existing model for the simulation of navigability conditions fed by different types of data and monitored

by sensors measuring the level of water in different sections of the river. Also, there are plans to use acoustic emission sensors and radar inspection to check the infrastructure.

We should keep in mind that the Synchronodal transport can be disrupted if the availability of the infrastructure is not efficiently organized. This can occur in inland shipping when vessels need to deliver containers to different terminals in a single port, leading to congestion and putting the delivery reliability of the synchronodal service at risk [67]. Despite the use of planning apps to provide insight into traffic on the quays, congestion has still occurred in the past year. Waiting times can also arise due to the use of different window times at terminals.

Based on what is discussed above, there is a need and possibility for designing a service to control and monitor the navigability of waterways in the corridor. This service should also be able to predict any potential obstacles, such as a lack of water, increased subsurface sand, or the lack of infrastructure ability. The creation of such a service can be the part of the initial plan for corridor management in CRISTAL.

External data

The navigability of the synchronodal corridor is impacted by various external factors too, including the availability of multimodal data such as rail systems, roads, terminals, ports, and parking spaces, as well as weather conditions. In order to manage these factors effectively, it is important to understand the impact they have on the corridor and the ways in which they can be managed.

The availability of multi-modal data is a crucial aspect of the synchronodal corridor management system. This data can include information on the capacity of rail systems, the location of terminals and ports, and the availability of parking facilities. This information can be used to optimize the routing of containers and to ensure that congestion at terminals and ports is minimized. Additionally, real-time monitoring of traffic conditions on roads can be used to adjust routes and avoid congestion, thus improving the efficiency of the system.

Weather conditions can also have a significant impact on the navigability of the synchronodal corridor. For example, heavy rain or snow can cause flooding or slippery roads, leading to delays and disruptions in the transportation of containers. To mitigate these risks, real-time weather information can be used to adjust routes and to ensure that vessels and vehicles are operated in safe conditions. Additionally, contingency plans can be developed to respond to adverse weather conditions and to minimize their impact on the corridor. Table 13 shows the data needed for planning synchronodality in summary.

Traffic data in the waterways is another important component of synchronodal corridor management. This data provides information about the movement of ships along the waterways, including details such as speed, direction, and location. By monitoring this data, it is possible to identify areas of congestion, as well as potential bottlenecks in the system. This information can then be used to optimize the scheduling and routing of ships, helping to minimize delays and increase the efficiency of the synchronodal system. In particular, traffic data for the current inland ships in the waterways can provide valuable insights into the performance of the system, and can be used to identify areas where improvements can be made to increase the overall efficiency of the synchronodal corridor.

Table 13 Data needed for planning synchronomodality [41]

Orders	Services	Network
Origin terminal	Terminal start	Start terminal
Destination terminal	Terminal end	End terminal
Number of containers (TEU)	Transport mode	Energy truck
Weight (tones)	Distance	Energy train
Time availability	Available capacity (TEU)	Energy barge
Time to deliver	Capacity flexibility (TEU)	Factor CO ₂ truck
Time to deliver (flexibility)	Start time	Factor CO ₂ train
Distance	End time	Factor CO ₂ barge
	Costs	
	Environmental	
	Transshipment costs	
	Transshipment environmental impact	

In this stage, we will delve into the optimization service for optimizing multi-modal transports, which considers both cost and emission models. We briefly discuss the optimization modelling of these tools in follow.

Optimal Routing Planning service

The optimization service model can optimize the utilization of the Synchronodal Corridor Management System network resources and simulate a synchronodal transport network as defined in [46]. It considers multiple commodities with origin-destination pairs and multiple transport operator services, accounts for different types of cargo and their costs and environmental impact, and considers multiple transportation service patterns. The optimization criteria can aim to minimize global costs and minimize global transport environmental impact, and the model can include a stochastic transportation case to account for uncertainties in transport and logistics processes. Discussions on the costs of transportation, including transshipment services, are considered in the next part.

Modelling Intermodal Transport Costs in a Synchronodal Corridor Management System

The cost of synchronodal services is complex and difficult to set in advance, but customers require a secure and known price. Cost is one of the main factors for the users of SCMS [67]. The operational

processes of intermodal transport involve many actors and often deviate from planned execution, making it difficult to calculate transport costs.

There are various cost models discussed in the literature [41], including the models of [69], [53], [61], [55], and [59]. The bottom-up approach to modelling intermodal transport costs offers transparency in cost composition and enables effective analysis and evaluation of the costs involved in intermodal transportation.

We can focus on the development of a cost model for simulating real transport costs in Europe, covering road, rail, and inland waterway transport. What we can suggest is the cost model can have a bottom-up approach and will allow the calculation of comparable cost values for any type of transport routes and volumes, based on [41]. The cost structure model includes four calculation modules: road, rail, waterway, and transshipment costs. The total costs are determined as a summation of costs generated by each transport mode and transshipment processes.

Emission Control Service in Synchronodal Corridor Management System

To measure environmental efficiency, various environmental indicators can be used. CO₂ emissions are commonly the primary focus, but there are multiple other emissions that can be measured in air, water, and soil. Although a large number of indicators can provide comprehensive information, it may lead to a loss of clarity. Therefore, the following approaches have been adopted to reduce the number of indicators while still producing meaningful results [64] [41].

- Combining all environmental impacts into a single performance indicator
- Grouping certain emissions into an impact category
- Aggregating sum parameters (e.g., cumulative energy demand)

CO₂ emissions can be categorized under greenhouse gas emissions, which are considered the leading cause of global warming. Other greenhouse gases, such as methane or nitrous oxide, are converted into CO₂ equivalents. The cumulative energy demand, on the other hand, represents resource consumption and is calculated by adding the energy consumption of all process steps in a common unit. In road transport, this includes not only fuel consumption but also energy consumption during fuel production, vehicle manufacture, and disposal. As the cumulative energy demand in road transport is primarily driven by fossil fuels, it has a strong correlation with greenhouse gas emissions [64].

Different approaches and methods for measuring CO₂ emissions in freight transport have been described in academic literature. The results can vary by up to 30% based on the definition of freight transport activities, precision of data sources, and consumption data for each transport mode [54] Figure 18 shows four examples, based on a study of British road freight transport by [54], of how CO₂ emissions were calculated for Heavy Goods Vehicle (HGV) transports of a certain weight. These methods require key indicators such as average distance travelled, fuel consumption, average load weight, etc. to determine the CO₂ output for a given period and thus calculate the carbon footprint of a transport relation.

Figure 18 Differing approaches to the calculation of territorial estimates of CO₂ [54]

In accordance with [54] the environmental effects of logistics activities cannot be directly measured but are estimated using average values from various data sources and software tools [60]. Therefore, the calculation of CO₂ equivalents in road freight transportation may result in varying values, but still provide a clear direction for selecting a green transport mode.

4. SCMS architecture

4.1 Overview of the system architecture

The Synchro-modal Corridor Management System (SCMS) is a unified system that introduces the exchange of standardized real-time messages to effectively predict natural or man-made corridor disruptions in order to effectively support uninterrupted operation in given transport networks, increasing the resilience of the entire transport system. Based on that, the system will incorporate a series of services that extend from conveying timely alerts to supporting critical decision making or extracting the optimal multi-modal route.

The operation of the introduced system of services could not be feasible without the proper input data. This is due to the need of the implemented algorithms and models for both raw and processed data stemming from both the operational and the geospatial characteristics of each IWW itinerary. Additionally, a few algorithms require data that include either advanced knowledge or even targeted predictions related to the operational specifications of the IWW, such as the quantified probability of the navigability of a given river for a reasonable upcoming interval.

The aforementioned types of data pertaining the IWW operations of the current project are mostly part of the processes performed in Work Package 2 (WP2 - Sensors Data Acquisition System) and Work Package 5 (WP5 - Digital Twin), respectively. However, some additional data could come from external sources, such as third party systems. Since WP2 focuses on the development of sensors for monitoring the navigability conditions of IWW, technologies for supporting the preventive maintenance of IWW infrastructures, as well as software architectures for data integration and processing, it is an ideal source of information for the implemented SCMS. On the other hand, the objective of the WP5 to export forecasts of events applying artificial intelligence, as well as suggest measures for action in the case of thresholds being exceeded or restrictions not being adhered to for certain events, renders it of crucial importance for feeding the SCMS.

The aim of the SCMS platform is all of its services to be part of a unified User Interface (UI) through which the user can interact with the implemented services and their deduced models and algorithms. Based on the above, the research team of the project depicted their view of the overall architecture of the SCMS functionality in Figure 19.

Figure 19 Corridor Management System Architecture

The detailed description of the individual components presented in Figure 19 takes place in the following sections.

Main components and system layers interactions

As illustrated in Figure 19, the Corridor Management System architecture can be summarized into three core components. The first component is the SCMS data lake and data connectivity layer, pertains to the input data sources to the system. The connectivity with multiple information sources will be achieved through Application Programming Interface (API) calls among the SCMS and the respective information brokers. The core data sources are expected from the WP2's (Sensors Data Acquisition System) and WP5's (Digital Twin) outcomes as well as external operational systems which will share information with the SCMS. Especially georeferenced data sources from existing systems (locks, bridges, harbour cranes, ports, roads, sensors, rivers, buoys, and ships) are to be considered for easy plug in to the system. Third party data could derive from: (a) River Information Services (RIS), such as water level, fairways, and obstructions, (b) operational activity, like orders, maintenance records, maintenance schedule, and inspection records, (c) historical weather conditions and weather forecasts, as well as (d) predictions, like predictive maintenance and navigability probability.

The second core component encompasses internal System management functionalities and services enabling tools of the SCMS. The Middleware Layer contains the operations' management tools and services section, as well as the configuration and data management layer. SCMS database is managing (near) real-time data as well as historical data and generated metadata. The Application component corresponds to the external services Layer of the SCMS that will be available to the users. There will be four main services that will be made available through the SCMS's User Interface (UI) to the users. The

external services are properly associated to a number of distinct enabling subservices that are part of the Middleware layer as shown in Figure 19.

The first service of the Application Layer is “Early Detection & Info Service”, which pertains to (i) the collection of sensor data stemming from WP2’s processing, as well as data from external systems, such as geospatial, weather and live tracking data. Technically, the service is responsible for fetching the required data from the corresponding brokers to the SCMS’s database. Additionally, (ii) the processing of data for anomalies detection is also supported by the service. Data from different sources are combined and checked against rules of common practice and thresholds that are either predefined as fixed values (based on actors’ prior domain knowledge or are inserted by the end-user). The “Early Detection & Info Service” is (iii) publishing the anomaly detection or the discrepancy info that is either calculated or given through a “push notification” mechanism based on predefined list of the appropriate stakeholders who need to be informed about the alert at the given time. It then generates alert messages towards actors containing information about the anomalies affecting their operation in a near real-time process. Finally, the service will incorporate accuracy and reliability assessment techniques for the received data & sources.

The second service, is the “Disruption Impact estimation Service”, is aiming at efficiently calculating and classifying the severity of upcoming disruptions throughout the IWW corridor, as well as at estimating the inferred effects that will occur due to the expected anomaly or disruption. Regarding the severity estimation of the disruption, the service will be able to classify the upcoming event into discrete scales of severity (low, medium, high, etc.), typology of impact to operations and categories of affected stakeholders. A knowledge hub is foreseen as part of the services in order to enable the more detailed possible description of the disruption impact: i.e., low waters may affect the navigability of all vessels or some of them depending on their characteristics, flood will constraint the capacity of a category of infrastructure or service of IWW, etc. The estimated impact of the disruption may also be associated to operations of the involved bodies related to river transport and the other modal transport networks infrastructure and services that are part of the Synchromodal Corridor. (ports/terminals and operators of the available means of transport). Environmental and economic impacts expressed in time and cost are considered by the service. Typical examples of operational impact estimation could be the estimation of the queue of stacked ships at the involved ports to support the management of ships waiting to enter the ports, the overcapacity situation in a container terminal due to the disruption effect, or the volumes of critical goods that need to be managed by alternative modes.

Impact estimation of disruptions is a task typically enabled by infrastructure Digital Twin assessing possible scenarios of the “to be” situation when disruption occurs. In this context, this service very much focuses on the best possible use of the digital twin outcomes and therefore the service is designed to “consume” information of possible upcoming disruptions effect from the Digital Twin’s (WP5) data broker, which will be combined with historically available data on the impact of past disruptions of the knowledge hub. This type of information is related with the duration of the predicted anomaly/disruption, (time to restore the normal flow of transport and the operations to the specific IWW associated to the predicted severity of disturbance in a waterway, etc.) and best strategy through the recovery process (i.e., choice between DO-NOTHING and wait at the current position or ACTION for example modifying the planned route and alternative modes use, or benefit from other services of IWW (guidance for using the range of services provided in the toolbox or elsewhere etc.).

The “[Action Toolbox Service](#)” is the third service provided by the SCMS and contains a set of sub-services that facilitate the stakeholders under adverse conditions to plan and implement an alternative operation as part of the actors’ recovery actions. The services are dedicated to transport and logistics providers and the IWW ecosystem stakeholders. The first sub-service, is “Re-routing Decision Support” and provides assistance to involved actors and users of IWW, for comparing alternatives and options of other modes serving their needs given the fact that a discrepancy was forecasted on the particular river corridor IWW operations. By considering other modes service availability on deviating routes and the user requirements (cargo requirements, time & cost parameters, locations of involved in flows to be diverted, special conditions etc.) the service is able to make the best suggestion for deciding the next move for each involved actor.

The “Action Toolbox Service” offers an additional sub-service, called “Sychromodal Re-Routing”. Practically, it pertains to the recommendation of the optimal alternative route of multiple means of transport to any cargo owner of logistics operator scheduled to an IWW service that will be disrupted. By Incorporating schedule, capacity and operations planning and availability data from modal systems other than IWW and combining them with transport & logistics requirements, the “Sychromodal Re-Routing” could operate. Practically, the user of the service will be given the possibility to choose the exact criterion based on which the algorithm will calculate/optimize the re-routing for recommending alternatives. The criteria currently considered for implementation in the context of the service are: (a) the Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA), (b) the predicted CO₂ emissions, (c) the projected cost or (d) possible combinations. The implementation of the above is subject to data availability and it is foreseen to be customized at the level of the pilot cases as a way for validation before generalization.

The “Action Toolbox Service” contains another sub-service, named “Digital Services for Supporting Sychromodality”, which is actually a set of services by itself. Sychromodal solutions in general, rerouting of cargo in particular and adaptation of initial planning, especially when it is to occur on short time, is a difficult problem. The planner needs to be flexible and able to manage differences in cost or timing of the services, storage requirement at intermediate stops, new and dynamic ETA calculation, contracts alteration and new contracts creation, compliance with additional regulation etc. In order to support the planner in executing his/her task the Sychromodality supporting service is developed as a catalogue and inventory of digital services and tools which will be either embedded or interconnected to SCMS platform in line with the Digital Transport & Logistics Forum guidelines for federated logistics platform and services. During the life cycle of the project the services to be developed or interconnected will fulfil the pilots’ actors’ requirements and after the project duration more services may be adopted as part of the platform exploitation. The currently considered catalogue of planning supporting services (exploiting background knowledge of partners) is related to track and trace provisioning along the corridor, e-documentation, traffic monitoring, cargo bundling, and on-demand warehousing. The planning supporting inventory may consider multiple services and its final composition will be co-decided with the involved and affected stakeholders.

The last service under the Application Layer is the “[Corridor Observatory](#)”. This is actually a Transport & Logistics operations dashboard and corridor resilience benchmarking tool. It will integrate a variety of static and real-time Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) as well as critical operational information derived from the pilots of CRISTAL related to the IWW transportation & Sychromodal alternatives. In any given IWW, the Corridor Observatory could capture (subject to data availability) metrics related to: (a) the traffic flow in the involved ports, (b) the performance of the individual operations of the river and of other modes

transportation, and (c) the disruptions recovery & the continuity of operations and navigability level of the IWW itself. The SCMS Corridor Observatory is not aiming at calculating massive list of KPIs but rather focusing on implementing added value KPIs and corridor benchmarking. In this context, it is foreseen that the specific SCMS services will be capable to provide input regarding general performance data and KPIs from operations at the pilot site systems who also have the role and the responsibility to monitor infrastructure or individual activities and operations of the involved actors in the corridor transport modes. Resilience KPIs will be calculated on the basis of historical data that will populate the knowledge base and events monitoring during the life cycle of the project.

The specific KPIs per pilot will depend on the goals and objectives of the stakeholders and the types of data available. The initial use cases of the above design are presented in the Annex II.

The final component of the SCMS architecture is the User Interface (UI). This is the portal through which the users can interact with the implemented services based on their level of access. Thus, the users of the SCMS can insert the necessary input parameters for each particular service and get an illustrated output for the respective request. Additionally, having a graded access operators and field experts could also set and, then modify, the thresholds upon which a disruption is defined per use case. Finally, in order for the services to interoperate with other systems, the synchro-modal corridor management system can be built upon the principles of the federated architecture that is tested within CEF FENIX project and can use the FENIX Connector technology which consists of three main functionalities: identity manager, broker and data exchange.

4.2 Data flow and data management

A comprehensive view of the types of the required data for all the services, including the aforementioned KPIs, is illustrated in Table 14.

Table 14 Proposed typology of data for the SCMS operation

Services	Data Type	Description
Early Detection & Info Service	Sensor Data	Status regarding locks, bridges, harbor cranes, ports, roads, rivers, ships, water level
	External Data	Operational activity (orders, maintenance schedule etc), weather conditions, processed metadata
Impact Identification Service	Container Terminal/Port Performance [72]	Dwell time, unloading time, productivity of the crane (box/crane/hour), container yard annual capacity
	Cost estimation for stakeholders – decision rerouting or leave products at port [72]	Timestamp of disruption, duration of disruption, cost of shipping by water, by rail, (by road), daily cargo value for each company, ton-miles shipped by water and by rail, discount rate for on-time delivery, penalty cost for late delivery
	Level of severity [72]	Type of disruption, duration of disruption, details of vessels

Action Toolbox Service	Vessel's information [73]	<p>Length and width of the vessel, draught</p> <p>Vessel's type, official name, flag</p> <p>Course & speed of the vessel, heading</p> <p>Given coordinates of the ship at a specific period of time</p>
	Cargo data [73]	<p>Unit of cargo (e.g container), type of cargo (e.g. dangerous goods) loaded or empty, status of cargo (e.g on shore, on board, en route)</p>
	Port parameters [74]	<p>Country/region/port of loading and unloading, origin and destination of cargo, arrivals and departures</p>
	ETA CO ₂ emissions Track & Trace	<p>Estimated time of arrival (ETA) is typically a temporal/date/time data type.</p> <p>CO₂ emissions can be considered a quantitative or numerical data type, typically measuring amounts or concentrations.</p> <p>Track and Trace refers to the ability to track a package or item as it moves through the delivery process. This could be considered as categorical or location data type, with each tracking point being a different location and each package being a different category.</p>
Observatory (KPIs)	Route Cost Metrics	<p>Includes order processing, administration, inventory carrying costs, warehousing and transportation costs.</p>
	Fuel consumes by freight transport [75]	<p>Aims to improving vehicle energy efficiency, by showing the relation between total fuels consume and weigh. The transport system is more efficient if the quantity of goods is higher than the consumed fuel.</p> $\frac{\sum W_i}{ADT} * C_i \text{ [Kg per Litre]}$ <p>W_i = Annual total weight of goods transported by a unit [Kg]</p> <p>ADT = Annual distance travelled of the unit [Km]</p> <p>C_i = unit of fuel consumption in [Km/litre]</p>
	Total CO ₂ emissions for travel (multiple modes) freight [75]	<p>Shows the energy use for freight transportation using several transport modes, and the energy intensities of each mode.</p> $\frac{\sum W_i}{ADT} * S * ADT * E_n \text{ [gCO}_2 \text{ per km]}$ <p>$\frac{\sum W_i}{ADT}$ = performance of freight transport [Kg per Km]</p> <p>S = Modal shares in total activity</p> <p>E_n = Energy consumption of a certain transport mode [gCO₂]</p>

		ADT = Annual distance travelled of the unit [Km]
	Performance of freight transport	<p>Aims to improving vehicle energy efficiency, by showing the relation between distance and weigh. The transport system is more efficient if the quantity of goods is higher than the distance.</p> $\frac{\sum W_i}{ADT} [Kg \text{ per } Km]$ <p>W_i = Annual total weight of goods transported by a unit [Kg]</p> <p>ADT= Annual distance travelled of the unit [Km]</p>
	Total time vessels spend in the queue [76]	<p>Time spent by ships in the queue during the dredging activities</p> <p>Total ship waiting time</p> <p>Working hours of dredging</p>
	Evaluation of disruption-based models	<p>Predicted vs actual duration of disruption</p> <p>Predicted vs actual time of disruption</p>
	Total transportation costs per shipment	The total cost of transporting goods from origin to destination, including all costs associated with vessel operation, maintenance, and infrastructure development.
	Maintenance costs per unit	<p>The trend of maintenance costs per unit produced and how they positively or negatively impact life cycle costs.</p> $maintenance \ unit \ cost = \frac{total \ maintenance \ cost}{standard \ units \ produced}$
	Transport Operator Benefits [77]	<p>This indicator aims to represent the transport operator benefits due to changes in transport revenues. The KPI provides an estimate of the impact of pricing policies on transport revenues.</p> $OBi = Ps2 * Qp2 - Ps1 * Qp1$ <p>$Ps1$ & $Ps2$ = the tolls paid</p> <p>$Qp1$ & $Qp2$ = traffic units that bear the cost of toll</p> <p>The KPI is obtained separately using transport, by discounting the future flow according to the formula:</p> $Transport \ Operator \ Benefits = \sum_{i=1, n} [OBi / (1+r)^n] / Pop$ <p>Pop = the population resident at the base year</p> <p>r = is the discount rate adopted and</p>

		n is the time of the analysis
	Availability of Waterway Infrastructure [78]	<p>The purpose of this indicator is to present the availability of the core waterway itself.</p> $\frac{365 - \text{Total stop/days per yr.}}{\text{Total nav. days/yr.}}$ <p>Total stop/days per yr = total stop of navigation on a specific waterway section measured in days per year</p> <p>Total nav. Days/yr = total navigable days per year</p>
	Stop navigation due to high water level [78]	<p>The main purpose of this performance metric is to indicate the impact of high-water levels on the inland waterway</p> $\frac{\text{Total high water/days yr}}{\text{Total nav. Days/yr}}$ <p>Total high water/days yr = stop of navigation on a specific waterway section due to high water measured in days per year</p> <p>Total nav. Days/yr = total navigable days per year</p>
	Ship's turn round time [79]	The ship's turn round time in the port is the primary indicator to show the total time spent by a vessel at the port from its arrival at reporting station till its departure from the reporting station.
	Average output per ship berth day [79]	<p>Average ship berth day output is the total cargo handled by the vessel sailed divided by the total stay at the working berth during the year</p> $\text{Average Ship Berth} - \text{Day output} = \frac{\text{Total Cargo handled by Vessels sailed}}{\text{Total Stay at Working Berth}}$
	Average pre-berthing waiting time [79]	<p>This indicator calculates the time taken by a ship from its arrival at the anchorage (reporting station) till it starts its movement to the working berth</p> $\text{Average Pre} - \text{Berthing Day Waiting time} = \frac{\text{Total Pre} - \text{berthing time of vessels sailed}}{\text{Total Number of Vessels sailed}}$

Data flow and data management are important concepts in the field of information technology and computing. More specifically, it refers to the movement of data from one place to another within a system, or between systems. It includes the processes and procedures for collecting, storing, transforming, and transmitting data, as well as the flow of control through a system. Effective data flow is essential for ensuring the accuracy, consistency, and reliability of data.

Data management, on the other hand, involves the processes and techniques used to store, organize, and manage data. This includes defining data structures and relationships, setting up data security and privacy controls, and establishing backup and recovery procedures. Good data management practices ensure that data is easily accessible, retrievable, and usable when needed.

The effective management of data flow and data management is crucial for projects like the SCMS, as it directly impacts their ability to make informed decisions, optimize their operations, and achieve their goals. It requires a thorough understanding of the business needs, the technology infrastructure, and the regulatory environment. Thus, the implementation of effective data flow and data management strategies requires a systematic and well-planned approach.

The followed data flow and data management in the Synchronodal Corridor Management System can be analysed in the following way [80], [81], [82]:

1. *Data Collection:* Data is gathered from a variety of sources, including transportation companies, cargo monitoring devices, and customs officials, in a synchronodal corridor management system. The data consists of crucial information such as cargo status, location, and projected arrival time.
2. *Data Integration:* In a centralized system, the gathered data is combined and processed for analysis. Standardizing the data format and converting it into a format that the system can readily understand and use are both parts of this procedure.
3. *Data Processing:* The data is then analysed to produce real-time insights on the performance of the corridor and forecast possible bottlenecks and delays. To ensure efficient and economical movement of products, the data is also utilized to improve the allocation of resources like trucks and railways.
4. *Data Storage:* The transformed data is kept in a central database and may be accessed and examined as required. The data should be accurate, safe, and simple to access, according to the data management system.
5. *Data Visualization:* Dashboards, reports, and maps are created from the processed data to give viewers a real-time view of how the synchronodal corridor is doing. These visualizations assist stakeholders in decision-making and raise the effectiveness of the transportation system.

4.3 Explanation of scalability, interoperability, and flexibility

A system's capacity to manage rising service demand without being overburdened is referred to as scalability. This means that a synchronodal corridor management system should be capable of accommodating increasing freight quantities and managing increasingly complicated logistical operations as necessary [83].

The capacity of various systems, platforms, and technologies to operate together without difficulty is referred to as interoperability. To maintain a seamless and effective supply chain, a synchronodal corridor

management system should be able to interact with other transportation systems and technology, such as shipping containers and GPS tracking [84].

A system's flexibility is its capacity to adjust to shifting circumstances and demands. This means that a synchromodal corridor management system should be able to adapt to changes in demand, market circumstances, and laws and update the transportation plan as necessary [28]. As a result, the system is able to respond more quickly and nimbly to supply chain demands.

From an operational perspective, in order to reduce the susceptibility of the transportation infrastructure to natural disasters and other man-made or natural calamities, the SCMS integrates both new and existing tools, models, and services. In this way, it improves the resiliency and seamless operation of passenger transportation and logistics networks using the existing infrastructure. With the proper system architecture, it encourages synchromodality and improves synchromodal flows along the corridors connected to the IWW. It also boosts visibility and monitoring (including monitoring of emissions) along the transportation networks enhancing the ability of multiple operators to work together and make decisions.

Based on the above, the scalability, interoperability, and flexibility specifications are incorporated into the design of their Synchromodal Corridor Management System (SCMS) in the following ways:

1. *Scalability:* We designed the SCMS to be highly scalable so that it can handle an increasing volume of cargo and transport requests. This could be achieved through the use of cloud-based infrastructure and distributed systems that allow the system to dynamically allocate resources as needed. The system's architecture is also designed to support the use of parallel processing and load balancing techniques to ensure that the system can handle large amounts of data and requests in real-time.
2. *Interoperability:* The SCMS is designed to be highly interoperable so that it can work seamlessly with other systems and technologies. We aim to achieve this by using FENIX connectors, which provide a standardized interface for connecting different systems and technologies. FENIX connectors enable the SCMS to communicate with other systems and technologies in a standardized way, allowing for the exchange of data and the seamless integration of different systems.
3. *Flexibility:* The SCMS is designed to be highly flexible so that it can adapt to changing business requirements and user needs. This is to be achieved through the use of a modular design that allows for the addition or removal of system components as needed. The system's architecture also supports the use of different transport modes and routing strategies, allowing the system to adapt to changes in transport conditions and user preferences. Additionally, the system is designed to be highly configurable, with customizable business rules and workflows that can be tailored to specific use cases and user needs.

Overall, the incorporation of scalability, interoperability, and flexibility specifications into the design of the SCMS for inland waterways ensures that the system can handle the complex and dynamic nature of inland waterway transport, while also being able to adapt to changing user needs and requirements.

4.4 Technical Requirements and specifications

Security measures

To increase the effectiveness and sustainability of supply chain operations, a synchromodal corridor management system combines and optimizes the utilization of many modes of transportation, such as rail, road, and sea. However, the following is a list of some of the fundamental technical specifications [85]:

1. *Interoperability*: In order to reduce duplication of effort and guarantee correct information sharing, the system should be able to communicate and share data easily with other transportation management systems, such as cargo management systems.
2. *Real-time monitoring and tracking*: To lessen ambiguity and improve decision-making, the system should offer real-time insight into the flow of items, including location, status, and anticipated arrival timeframes.
3. *Route optimization*: The system must be able to assess several transportation alternatives, recommending the most effective route after accounting for elements like cost, time, and environmental impact.
4. *Predictive analytics*: The system should be able to estimate demand using historical data analysis and prediction algorithms to allocate resources and schedule transportation in an educated manner.
5. *Data security*: Sensitive data, such as customer and business-critical information, should be safeguarded and secured from unauthorized access by the system.

Some of the main technological parameters and needs for a synchromodal corridor management system are listed above. It is significant to note that these specifications might change based on the unique demands and specifications of the stakeholder putting the system into place.

Any transportation management system, especially synchromodal corridor management systems, must prioritize security since they frequently store and handle sensitive data including customer and business-critical data. Synchromodal corridor management systems should put in place a thorough set of security measures to protect the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of data [27].

Below are some measures that we aim to take in the context of the present project:

1. *Access control*: The system should have systems in place to monitor and log access, and access should only be granted to authorized users and roles.
2. *Encryption*: To avoid unwanted access and theft, sensitive data, such as customer and business-critical information, should be encrypted both in storage and during transport.
3. *Firewalls*: Firewalls should be used to secure the system and stop harmful traffic from entering.
4. *Intrusion detection and prevention*: System safeguards, such as intrusion detection and prevention systems, should be in place to identify and stop illegal access.
5. *Data backup and recovery*: A strong data backup and recovery plan should be in place for the system to guarantee data availability in the event of a catastrophe or other disruption.

These are some of the most important security precautions to take into account while setting up a synchromodal corridor management system. It is essential to remember that the individual demands and requirements of the company will determine the precise security measures needed. A regular evaluation and update of the security measures is also necessary to make sure they continue to be effective in the face of changing security threats.

Compliance with EU regulations and standards

To maintain its efficacy and efficiency in controlling the transportation of commodities over inland waterways inside the EU, a synchromodal corridor management system must adhere to numerous European Union (EU) legislation and standards.

The system must, first and foremost, adhere to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) of the EU, which establishes guidelines for the protection of natural people with regard to the processing of personal data. This implies that the system must guarantee the security and privacy of any personal data processed as well as the right of individuals to access and modify their personal data [86].

Additionally, the system must abide by all EU-issued environmental protection rules and directives, including those that address waste management, the prevention of air and water pollution, and the conservation of species and ecosystems. This calls on the system to think about how its operations could influence the environment and to take action to lessen any negative effects [73].

Moreover, Inland Waterway Navigation (IWN) Directive, which establishes uniform guidelines for the safe and effective operation of inland waterway transport in the EU, is one such legislation that the system must also abide with. This covers legislation governing inland waterways infrastructure development and operation as well as laws governing safety, security, and environmental preservation [88].

The system must also adhere to the Technical Specifications for Interoperability (TSI) of the EU for the inland waterway transport industry. For the interoperability of the inland waterways system of the EU, the TSI establishes uniform technical standards and processes. This contains specifications for the interoperability of information and communication systems as well as for the technical and operational compatibility of inland waterways systems.

In order for a synchromodal corridor management system for inland waterways transport to function successfully and efficiently while simultaneously safeguarding the environment and individual rights, it is imperative that it adhere to different EU legislation and standards. As a result, the network of inland waterways in the EU is made sustainable and safe for the transit of products.

Analysis of hardware and software specifications

For hardware specifications, the synchromodal corridor management system should have sufficient processing power and memory to handle large amounts of data and perform complex calculations, as well as robust storage solutions to store and retrieve information quickly. The system should also have a reliable network connectivity to enable seamless integration with other systems.

For software specifications, the use of Python programming language and the Flask framework provides a versatile and efficient platform for developing the synchromodal corridor management system. Python's extensive libraries for data analysis and manipulation, combined with Flask's lightweight and modular design, make it easier to build a scalable and maintainable system [84].

SQL Server as the database management system provides the system with a robust and reliable platform for storing and retrieving data. SQL Server has a rich set of features, such as advanced data security, scalability, and support for transaction processing, which are essential for managing large amounts of data in a synchromodal corridor management system.

The use of FENIX Connectors, a set of tools for data integration, can further enhance the synchromodal corridor management system by allowing for seamless integration with other systems and data sources. This integration enables real-time data exchange and the ability to automate processes, leading to more efficient and effective management of the synchromodal corridors.

In conclusion, the hardware and software specifications for synchromodal corridor management systems should be carefully considered to ensure the system is robust, efficient, and able to integrate with other systems. The choice of Python and Flask framework as the programming language and framework, along with SQL Server as the database management system, and the possible use of FENIX Connectors provides a comprehensive platform for developing a synchromodal corridor management system that meets these requirements.

Integration with other systems

For supply chain operations to be effective and simplified, a synchromodal corridor management system (SCMS) for inland waterways must be integrated with other external systems [83], [84]. The external systems listed below can be connected with the SCMS for inland waterways:

1. *Transportation Management System (TMS)*: A TMS can be integrated with the SCMS to provide real-time updates on the status of shipments, enabling real-time decision making and better transportation management.
2. *Port Management System (PMS)*: A PMS provides information on vessel schedules, berth allocation, and cargo tracking. Integrating the PMS with the SCMS can improve the coordination of cargo handling at the port, reducing delays and increasing efficiency.
3. *Logistics Service Provider (LSP) Systems*: Integrating the SCMS with the systems of logistics service providers (LSPs) enables real-time tracking of shipments and the optimization of transportation routes and modes.
4. *Geographic Information System (GIS)*: A GIS can provide information on geographical features such as waterways, locks, and port facilities, enabling the SCMS to better predict potential bottlenecks and delays in the supply chain.
5. *Customs Systems*: Integrating the SCMS with customs systems can facilitate the smooth flow of cargo across borders, reducing the time and cost associated with customs clearance.

6. *Financial Systems*: Integrating the SCMS with financial systems can provide real-time updates on the cost of transportation, enabling better cost management and optimization of the supply chain.

In conclusion, the SCMS for inland waterways may be integrated with other external systems to give a full perspective of the whole supply chain, facilitating improved decision-making, lowering costs, and increasing the overall effectiveness of inland waterway freight transportation.

4.5 Functional specifications of main systems and components

The purpose of this section is to provide an overview of the SCMS intended capabilities, appearance, and interactions with users to be used as a kind of guideline and continuing reference point for the software developers for writing the programming code [89]. The main components that have been defined and described in the previous chapters of the present document are connected to the architecture for the system development described in 4.1 in order to provide the functionalities described in the section below.

Early Detection & alerts (ED&A) service for the SCMS

Early warning systems (EWS), and Multi-Hazard Early Warning Systems (MHEWS) are key elements of climate change adaptation and disaster risk reduction, and aim to avoid or reduce the damages caused by different kind of hazards [95]. To be effective, early warning systems need to actively involve the people and communities at risk from a range of hazards, facilitate public education and awareness of risks, disseminate messages and warnings efficiently and ensure that there is a constant state of preparedness and that early action is enabled.

Early warning systems include detection, analysis, prediction, and then warning dissemination followed by response decision-making and implementation. To be effective and complete, an early warning system needs to comprise four interacting elements namely:

1. Disaster Risk knowledge;
2. Detection, monitoring, analysis and forecasting of the hazards and possible consequences;
3. Warning dissemination and communication;
4. Preparedness and response capability.

Figure 20 4 elements of MHEWS [96]

In Europe there is a considerable experience with early warning systems, including ones for the hazards that are more relevant to waterways such as: flood and flash-flood risk, storms, heatwaves and droughts. Some EWS services are for more than one climate-related hazards (e.g., the first three in the list below); others focus on one specific hazard (e.g., the last three in the list below).

- **Meteoalarm** (<https://www.meteoalarm.org/en/>) – a joint effort from EUMETNET (The Network of European Meteorological Services), provides alerts in Europe for extreme weather events, including heavy rain with risk of flooding, severe thunderstorms, gale-force winds, heatwaves, forest fires, fog, snow or extreme cold with blizzards, avalanches or severe coastal tides.
- **Copernicus Climate Change Service, C3S**: (<https://climate.copernicus.eu/>) provides reliable high-quality climate data and tailored information for socio-economic sectors at the European level, which are surely relevant for climate change adaptation. In particular C3S provides specific operational service for the water sector (<https://climate.copernicus.eu/operational-service-water-sector/>) such as the
 - *“European hydrology and climate data explorer”* interactive web application that provides easy access to a range of climate impact indicators for water quantity, water quality and relevant meteorological climate impact indicators.
 - *“Hydrological seasonal forecast explorer”* interactive web application that presents monthly hydrological seasonal forecasts of river discharge from a hydrological ensemble using the SEAS5 seasonal forecasting system.
 - *Climate Data Store (CDS) toolbox* (<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/toolbox>) that links raw data to online computing power through a programming interface²; it allows creating applications in Python and to run them on CDS computers, allowing to

² The Climate Data Store (CDS) Application Program Interface (API) is a service providing programmatic access to CDS data; CDS API examples can be found here, <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/api-how-to>

retrieve and process data and to display the results in the format that suits specific needs. The CDS toolbox allows downloading graphs, maps and data, and also to share them with other users.

- **Risk Data Hub** (<https://drmkc.jrc.ec.europa.eu/risk-data-hub/#/>) of the Disaster Risk Management Knowledge Centre (DRMKC) managed by DG JRC provides curated EU-wide risk data via hosting datasets and through linking to national platforms.
- **European Drought Observatory** (<https://edo.jrc.ec.europa.eu/edov2/php/index.php?id=1111>) contains drought-relevant information from different data sources [97] that can be displayed and analysed through different tools; it includes also "Drought News" service provides an overview of the situation in case of imminent droughts.
- **Flood The European Flood Awareness System (EFAS)** supports preparatory measures before major flood events strike, particularly in the large trans-national river basins and throughout Europe in general (https://www.efas.eu/efas_frontend/#/home).
- **EuroHEAT** acts as a climate information decision support tool for Heatwaves and extreme heat and is accompanied by a guidance document.

Besides these large scales' initiatives, EWS have been designed and implemented at lower levels such as national, sub-national and regional/local. Emilia Romagna region (Italy), where the CRISTAL River Pilot Po is located, provides cutting edge technologies and services in that respect, including:

- **Flood and Drought Early Warning System of the Po River (FEWS Po and DEWS Po)** (Figure 21) provide hydrological forecast information using a multi-model approach for droughts and floods in the Po river basin, the system was developed in cooperation by National Department of Civil Protection (DPC), the Interregional Agency for the Po river (AIPO), the Po river Basin Authority and all Regions of the Po Basin. The FEWS Po and DEWS Po systems use real time data from monitoring network, radar and meteorological scenarios coupled with several numerical models capable to provide forecast during drought and flood events.
- **Weather Alert Web Portal** has been developed in parallel to the development and refinement of real-time hydro-meteorological monitoring technologies (Figure 22) (<https://allertameteo.regione.emilia-romagna.it/livello-idrometrico>) and a widespread risk communication programme.

Figure 21 Flood and Drought Early Warning System of the Po River (FEWS Po and DEWS Po) geoportal and service

Figure 22 Weather Alert Web Portal available for River Pilot Po (Italy)

The ED&A service for SCMS will have the following three main functions, as follows:

- a. **Real time (nowcasting) data/information of water level.**
 - i. ED&A service will provide water level for a pre-defined list of critical sections in quasi real time.
- b. **Forecast data/information of water level.**
 - i. ED&A service will provide water level for a pre-defined list of critical sections up to 10 days.
- c. **Predicted (near-term future) water level or discharge information.**

- i. ED&A service will provide, when feasible, climate indicators predicted in the near-term future (e.g., next 6 months) by connecting the ED&A to the EWA services available in Europe as previously described.

As for **real time and forecast services (a) and (b) respectively**, as far as the main Po River is concerned, all critical points are known and monitored mainly during low regimes (Figure 23 and Figure 24).

Figure 23 Monitored critical sections in the main Po River (Italy)

Figure 24 Data about critical sections identified in the Po River (Italy) available from AIPO geoportal³

³ <http://geoportale.agenziapo.it/web/index.php/it/dati-disponibili>

Starting from the information provided by the DEWS/FEWS Po EWA system (cfr. 3.4) and coupling numerical models (e.g., statistic or hydraulic models) calibrated using a long time series data related to each critical point along the river, AIPO will estimate, in the framework of CRISTAL project, a probability of navigability for each critical section (Figure 25).

Draught [cm]	Discharge [m ³ /s]																						
	50	100	150	200	250	300	350	400	450	500	600	700	800	900	1000	1500	2000	3000	4000	5000	8000	9000	10000
140	0%	0%	3%	15%	36%	56%	77%	83%	87%	91%	95%	97%	98%	99%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
160	0%	0%	0%	13%	35%	54%	76%	82%	86%	90%	95%	97%	98%	99%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
180	0%	0%	0%	10%	33%	53%	76%	82%	86%	90%	95%	97%	98%	99%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
200	0%	0%	0%	5%	29%	50%	74%	81%	85%	90%	94%	97%	98%	99%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
220	0%	0%	0%	0%	22%	45%	72%	79%	84%	89%	94%	96%	98%	99%	99%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
240	0%	0%	0%	0%	13%	39%	68%	76%	82%	87%	93%	96%	98%	99%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
260	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	30%	64%	73%	79%	85%	92%	95%	97%	99%	99%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Figure 25 Information provided by the CRISTAL ED&A service (from the DEWS/FEWS Po early warning systems) that can be inputted into the CRISTAL SCMS

With navigability information available for each reach (i.e., from one docking to the following one), each one including several critical points, AIPO will provide to shippers a forecast estimation related to the draught level. Alert information will be related to the specific use (e.g., they will be different for transportation and recreational uses); navigability information and related alerts are essential for planning and cost evaluation.

Draught [cm]	Reach	Now	+1gg	+2gg	+3gg	+4gg	+5gg	+6gg	+7gg	+8gg	+9gg	+10gg
140	Reach 1	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Yellow	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
	Reach 2	Green	Yellow	Red	Red	Red	Red	Yellow	Green	Green	Green	Green
	Reach 3	Green	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Green	Green	Green	Green
	Reach 4	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Yellow	Green	Green	Green
160	Reach 1	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red	Yellow	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
	Reach 2	Green	Yellow	Red	Red	Red	Red	Yellow	Green	Green	Green	Green
	Reach 3	Green	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Green	Green	Green	Green
	Reach 4	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Yellow	Green	Green	Green

Figure 26 Outputs of the ED&A service that will feed the digital twin (red – reach unavailable, orange – doubtful, green – available)

An End-User of the system may query water level relevant information when planning for a trip. ED&A service can provide Pop-up alerts in push mode on demand to the end-user.

As for the functional service related to **Predicted (near-term future) water level or discharge information (c)** web applications for EWS available at EU level and CDS (Climate Data Store) services from Copernicus, might be potentially connected to CRISTAL SCMS, through APIs; EU EWS have already defined functional specifications that may be modified (at least in their representation) to fulfil specific requirements of the envisaged CRISTAL IWW. The definition of the functional specifications must be done in a co-creative mode together with the stakeholders as part of CRISTAL pilots.

Early Detection & Alerts ED&A service to be connected to the CRISTAL SCMS can be differently defined in relation to different temporal phases in the disaster risk reduction (DRR) and climate change adaptation (CCA) cycle (Figure 27). CRISTAL will define the ED&A service for normal operating phase of the DRR/CCA cycle only, namely, for operational purposes (Step 2 of the DRR/CCA cycle) and for planning resilience and

mitigation strategies (Step 3 of the DDR/CCA cycle). The National Department for Civil Protection in Italy (DPC) is in charge and make available an ED&A service for the emergency operating phase of the DDR/CCA.

Figure 27 Disaster risk reduction (DRR) and climate change adaptation (CCA) cycle, DDR/CCA cycle⁴

Towards embedding ED&A service in the real-time operations management and decision support toolbox & services for obtaining navigability information by SCMS platform the following steps are envisaged

1. **Real time (nowcasting) data/information of water level.** The system will be configured to acquire data in real time as described in Table 1. The system processes the data by using AIPO data analytics methods to evaluate the water level and/or other KPIs with some frequency. The data is made available to the SCMS platform (and other CRISTAL components). Alerts can be generated by using pre-defined thresholds.
2. **Forecast data/information of water level.** The real-time data on the water level condition is supplied to the Digital Twin to generate short-term predictions of the water level for the pre-defined critical sections. Prediction outputs for those sections are made available to the SCMS platform.
3. **Predicted (near-term future) water level or discharge information.** Climate indicators are considered to produce near-term future water level information based on the current condition.

Synchromodal planning under uncertainty system

The Synchromodal planning under uncertainty system is integrating the functionalities of the Early Detections & alerts system described in the previous section, as well as the real-time operations management and decision support toolbox and the observatory. It aims to provide to inland waterways with a powerful suite of tools for optimizing and managing the complex and dynamic nature of inland waterway operations. The Synchromodal planning system helps to monitor and manage disruptions as well as to allocate resources, while the real-time operations management and decision support toolbox

⁴ https://www.cencenelec.eu/media/CEN-CENELEC/News/Workshops/2022/2022-02-11%20-%20City%20Resilience/prcwa_17727-2022.pdf

provides real-time information and decision support to operators and managers. Together, these functional specifications improve the efficiency and reliability of inland waterway transport, helping to ensure the smooth flow of goods and people.

The purpose of the current SCMS's planning system is to calculate and propose optimized alternative freight transport routes in the event of IWW disruptions, tying up other transport modes when deemed necessary (mainly focusing on rail). The objective is to ensure the uninterrupted flow of cargo along the corridor to which the designated IWW belongs. In this way, the reliability and durability of the entire runway transportation system will be enhanced, thus also leading to an increase in the durability and attractiveness of the IWW as part of this system.

To achieve its purpose, the system is designed to receive requests from stakeholders responsible for transport planning and process data from various external sources to arrive at and propose optimal solutions. It will also provide access to a toolbox of services that will support stakeholder decisions on cargo rerouting.

The main operational principles of the system can be described by the following flow:

1. A stakeholder (system user) responsible for scheduling cargo transportation through IWW will enter the system (platform) through a user interface and provide advance information on cargo and transportation characteristics such as time and point entry into the IWW, origin-destination and cargo volume, transport unit and any restrictions that may exist and can affect the transfer to other modes (e.g., dangerous, sensitive goods, exceptional size transport). A stakeholder (system user) responsible for the planning of the transportation of cargo through the IWW will enter the system (platform) through a UI and provide in advance information regarding the characteristics of the cargo and transportation, such as the time and point of entry to the IWW, the origin-destination and volume of cargo, the unit of transport and any possible limitations that may exist (e.g., dangerous goods).
2. The system will have an up-to-date database of the IWW infrastructure (canals, wharves & locks, barges) as well as the interfaces and core network of the other modes of transport. In addition, the user will continuously receive information including but not limited to: (a) (near) real-time alerts on IWW navigability for the short-term (hours) and medium-term (days) generated from processed raw input from installed sensors from the early detection and warning system described in the previous section, (b) notifications generated by infrastructure managers regarding infrastructure outages (e.g. scheduled maintenance or accidents preventing the use of the infrastructure) and any other type of notifications generated by infrastructure authorities, (c) medium/long term alerts triggered by outage predictions derived from Digital Twin algorithms that analyse collected sensor data related to maintenance needs or navigation, as well as duration estimates of all types of outages entered into the platform related to navigational issues, and (d) the availability of infrastructure (channels, wharves & locks) calculated through scheduled works and the availability of infrastructure (canals, quays & locks) calculated through the scheduled operations. All this input is translated into a list of geo-referenced and timed outages, including the severity level of these impacts, which are then stored in a database.
3. The system simulates cargo transportation based on user request and provided information utilizing Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA) and service availability under optimal conditions (i.e.,

full-service availability and no interruptions en-route) by calculating where and when the cargo is supposed to be. It also calculates the estimated cost, CO₂ and ETA of this original planned route.

4. The system then matches expected/existing disruptions from the list of geographic and defined disruptions (step 2) with the calculated route and generates alerts for potential bottlenecks that will also experience other impacts. These notifications are communicated to the system user.
5. Based on the affected parts of the original path, the system runs algorithms to find alternatives, considering the location of the interface points to the other modes and the availability of services. These alternatives may include shifting to other modes of transport (e.g., road or rail) for the entire journey or transshipment at intermediate hubs, considering whether the type of cargo allows this change. The system will also consider other side effects of disruptions, such as cargo stacking at ports that will require additional time to restore operations.
6. The estimated characteristics (cost, CO₂ and ETA) of all alternatives, the initial planned route and the option to do nothing and wait are presented to the system user to select the appropriate action.
7. Based on the user's chosen action, the system supports their decision by providing points of contact to book a new route (if selected) and an access to a toolbox of services (e.g., on-demand warehouse service if the decision is to wait).
8. Finally, the platform records the initial and final route selection and their characteristics in a database for future use (i.e., observatory, ML algorithms).

The functional specifications of the Synchronodal planning under uncertainty system and the real-time operations management and decision support toolbox are designed to be responsive to unforeseen disturbances that may occur during the transportation of cargo. These disruptions can range from unexpected weather events to traffic congestion or accidents on the waterways. To address these issues, the system can dynamically calculate and propose alternative routes to system users in real-time. This feature allows the system to respond quickly to any disruptions, minimizing the impact on the transport of cargo and improving the overall reliability of the network. By providing real-time information and decision support, the system helps operators and managers to make informed decisions quickly and efficiently, ensuring the smooth flow of goods and passengers on the inland waterways.

To finalize the functional specifications, it is important to define the system processes, user actions, data requirements, and user interface for a project before moving on to the next phase of development. This is because having a clear understanding of these elements is essential for building a successful project that meets the needs of its intended users.

As mentioned in section 4.1, the next project period will involve close cooperation with the project's technical partners and potential system users to define these elements in more detail. This process will likely involve a combination of meetings, brainstorming sessions, user testing, and other forms of collaboration to ensure that all stakeholders are aligned on the project's goals and vision.

5. Conclusions

The purpose of the present deliverable is to define the main requirements and specifications of a Synchronodal Corridor Management System for Inland Waterways that will be developed within the project to address the challenges emerging from natural and human caused disruptions. It constitutes the ground basis for the systems and technologies that will be developed or integrated in the following tasks of the WP3, leading to a system that will support the project objectives for increased reliability, resilience and attractiveness of the IWT systems. The system is focusing on IWW that are not part of the well-developed river network of northern Europe, since these rivers need also to have significant part and role in the EU transport system in order to achieve the goals set by the EU in alignment to the Paris Agreement and are expressed through recently established European Commission strategies such as the European Green Deal and the Sustainable and Smart Mobility Strategy.

Through the feedback received by the pilot site partners regarding the views and needs of key stakeholders who are operating in their sites, it appears that there are impacts and issues in the current processes of handling disruptions that they believe that could be supported from the planned Synchronodal Corridor Management System as this was shortly described to them. This description included the main services of early alerting, assessing the operational impacts of disruptions, proposing alternative solutions and supporting actions. Therefore, stakeholders already see the value in the CRISTAL proposition for the SCMS while they also suggested additional services that they believe that would be useful to be added to the future.

It should be noted however that at this early stage of the project it was not possible to include directly external stakeholders and engage them to the project processes. Instead, all the necessary knowledge has been collected through literature review and a questionnaire survey to the pilot leaders who have the required knowledge to a large extent due to their unique position in the IWW supply chains. The combination of an extensive and in-depth literature and SoA review with the direct input from pilots who provide their real-life experience and views as well as the realistic testing in the pilot sites will ensure the design of a feasible system that may answer to several significant problems that hinder the development of IWW transport. Once the solutions are defined, a workshop will take place engaging a wider audience also from outside the consortium for refining the SCMS value proposition.

In addition, all systems (including the SCMS) are based on data quality and availability, collaboration among stakeholders and information sharing in order to produce and offer quality services. To the extent that this is possible, the required change of mindset to achieve all the above will be attempted within the project duration. For this reason, it is essential to ensure that the interaction with stakeholders within and outside the consortium will continue during the entire lifecycle of the project. However, limitations that will remain (especially regarding data availability and information sharing) are likely to constrain the development of some services and functionalities of the SCMS that are part of the vision described in the first part of the document.

Finally, regarding the next activities of WP3, after the mapping of operational processes and data availability in the three pilot sites as well as the finalization of the Use Cases in the context of WP6, the list of services that will be part of the value proposition of the SCMS will be finalized and their development will begin as per the provisions of the GA.

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7. Appendices

Annex I

Questionnaire to project pilots

Q1. What is happening today when a disruption in the IWW occurs?

- **Who** is informing the transport operators & other stakeholders for the disruption (e.g. the infrastructure manager), **When** (e.g. immediately as the disruption happens if it is something unforeseen) and **How** (e.g. through a message or a website)?
.....

- **What the transport operators do usually:**

Wait for the disruption to end and for the IWW operations to go back to normal.

They move their cargo to another transport mode. Usually which one?
.....

Other option (please describe):
.....

- **Where do they base their decision to act (you can select more than one choice)?**

An estimation for the duration of the disruption

The type of cargo they are moving

The availability of other modes of transport

The expected cost of the transshipment to other mode(s)

The expected time required for the transshipment to other mode(s)

Possible contractual obligations and other legal issues. If possible, please elaborate:.....

Other (please specify):

- **What is the overall chain of actions when a disruption occurs? If you can, please describe shortly the overall process from the time a disruption occurs until the time that everything is addressed and the cargo resumes its trip to its destination.**
.....

Q2. Which are the main problems that transport operators are facing when a disruption occurs today (please rate the following statements: 1=strongly disagree, 2= disagree, 3= I don't know, 4= agree, 5 strongly agree)?

	Rate 1 to 5
• Significant increase in the cost of operations	
• Significance decrease of their reliability towards customers	
• There are no real alternatives available because of:	
- the type of cargo that is transported	
- the additional cost required	
- the additional time required	
- lack of efficient interfaces to other modes of transport (especially rail)	
- the duration of disruptions (are usually short and it is not worth looking for alternative choices)	
- other (please specify):	
• The information arrives late to support timely decisions	
• There is not enough visibility of the alternative options/Unaware of other options	
• Other (please specify):	

Q3. The Synchronodal Corridor Management System of CRISTAL is a system planned to provide the following services:

1. Produce early alerts of disruptions & notify the relevant stakeholders of IWT systems
2. Estimate the impact on operations of the identified disruptions
3. Proposition of alternatives to the IWW stakeholders to address the impacts of these disruptions including a possible mode change (concept of synchronomodality)
4. Support the decisions of stakeholders through a toolbox of services (e.g., rerouting tools, visibility services etc.)

Based on the description of the Synchronodal Corridor Management System (SCMS) services:

- **Which of the following issues do you believe that will be improved and how much (please rate from 1 to 5 where: 1= no change, 5= significant improvement)?**

	Rate 1 to 5
• Lack of visibility of the alternative choices	
• Reduction of reliability of IWT system	
• High cost for handling disruptions by the transport operators	
• Unawareness of the operational impacts of disruptions	
• Difficulty in connection to other modes of transport	
• Difficulty in planning the move of cargo under uncertainty (due to a disruption)	
• Timely notification of the disruptions & reaction from stakeholders	
• Other (please specify):	

- **Who you believe would be interested in having access to Synchronodal Corridor Management System besides the transport operators and why?**

.....

- **Who you believe that should be managing the Synchronodal Corridor Management System?**

.....

Q4. Are there additional services that would be useful to include now or in the future to the Synchronodal Corridor Management System beside the ones described in section 3 that could help the IWT systems deal with disruptions?

.....

Q5. Please provide any other comments/ information that you believe that are relevant to the handling of disruptions today at your pilot site and the development of the Synchronodal Corridor Management System.

.....

Annex II

SCMS implementation initial Use Cases

Use cases objectives

The term “Use Cases” is used to describe the scenarios and actions that a system can realise and which are directly related to the system requirements. The Use Cases are connected to the objectives that a system needs to achieve through its operation and usually include actions from the system user in order to define the requirements for the technical development of the system. In the present chapter, the generic Use Cases that are proposed for supporting the development of the CRISTAL Synchromodal Corridor Management System are presented.

In the next period following the submission of this deliverable, the generic Use Cases will be specified in detail in close collaboration with the project’s pilot and technical partners in the context of WP6. This will be done considering the planned implementation of technologies and concepts in the pilot sites, the pilot sites’ specific characteristics, and the availability of resources. For every pilot the UCs that better serve the project requirements will be selected and further developed in terms of description, specific actors involved, partners’ role, goals of the UC, main flow, and analysis & evaluation details.

- Use Cases for the early alert services

The purpose of this category of Use Cases is to showcase the services for alerting stakeholders for upcoming disruptions that will be produced consuming information that is produced outside the platform (sensors, digital twin, other platforms), aggregating and processing it. There are three distinct Use Cases described below:

UC1.1	
Title	Timely alert publication
Description	A service for timely alerting all relevant stakeholders for upcoming disruptions based on the alert information provided to the SCMS platform from the sensors systems developed in WP2. The alerts produced by the sensors systems are collected and matched to the relevant stakeholders of the transportation system and then a notification is sent through proper communication channels.
Goal of the use case	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create one central point for collecting sensors alerts and triggering actions for all deployed sensors • Create a list of the types of stakeholders and their needs for information • Timely disseminate the information to all relevant stakeholders (not only skippers) about upcoming disruptions to the IWT systems and thus to all relevant decision stages of the supply chain

Expected impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhance visibility of disruptions to all relevant actors of the supply chain • Improve navigability in cases of extreme weather events • Support faster decision making for the disruption handling (actions) for all relevant actors (e.g., LSPs) leading to a reduction of transit time and a related increase of efficiency
Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Logistics Service Providers • Transport companies • Infrastructure managers

UC1.2	
Title	Early alert assessment
Description	A service for utilising Big Data analytics and AI algorithms to define the operational impacts on the IWT system based on the input provided by the sensors systems and for informing relevant stakeholders. The service will also assess the severity of upcoming disruptions.
Goal of the use case	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide a timely estimation to all relevant stakeholders of the operational impacts emerging from the real or near-real life data from the sensors system deployed • Timely support the decision making in all relevant stages of the supply chain
Expected impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhance visibility of disruptions impacts to all relevant actors of the supply chain • Support faster decision making for the disruption handling (actions) for all relevant actors (e.g., LSPs) leading to a reduction of transit time and a related increase of efficiency
Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Logistics Service Providers • Transport companies • Infrastructure managers

UC1.3	
Title	Digital twin impact estimation
Description	A service for utilising the Digital Twin input regarding the impacts (expansion, duration, navigability etc) of upcoming disruptions to calculate the operational impacts in the IWT system and inform relevant stakeholders. The digital twin model will be developed to incorporate real-time data and weather data for an

	infrastructure early warning and infrastructure maintenance system, as well as to support corridor management. Digital twin predictive models will provide medium/long term alerts triggered from forecasts of disruptions coming from the Digital Twin algorithms which analyse the collected sensor data (regarding maintenance needs or navigability) and also estimations of the duration of all types of disruptions inserted to the platform that are related to navigability issues.
Goal of the use case	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employ state of the art digital technologies for impact estimation regarding the navigability of rivers in the short, medium and long term • Timely disseminate the information about the disruptions impacts to all relevant stakeholders for supporting the synchromodal planning in the transport corridor
Expected impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhance visibility of all types (short, medium, long term) disruptions impacts to relevant actors of the supply chain • Efficient planning under uncertainty in IWW and implementation of the concept of synchromodality • Support decision making at regional level regarding infrastructural needs and investments
Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Logistics Service Providers • Transport companies • Infrastructure managers

- Use cases for planning under uncertainty

The purpose of this category of Use Cases is to showcase the services for supporting the planning of IWT under uncertainty and promoting synchromodality. There are three distinct Use Cases described below:

UC2.1	
Title	Mapping of alternatives and availabilities
Description	A service for creating a data base of all the existing alternatives and interfaces between modes of transport that are available when a disruption occurs. This includes information such as the relevant available infrastructure & capacities, transshipment facilities and fixed routes of all modes.
Goal of the use case	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create one central point for collecting information about the alternatives and availabilities that can be utilised in the case of disruptions, • Create visibility of the feasible transport alternatives to all relevant stakeholders, • Support of the synchromodal planning

Expected impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhance visibility of alternative options along the transport corridor including all modes of transport, • Enhance communication/collaboration between the different modes of transport, • Support decision making regarding possible mode change for disruption handling • Increase efficiency of transportation
Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shippers/cargo owners • Logistics Service Providers • Transport companies • Infrastructure managers

UC2.2	
Title	Synchromodal route planning
Description	A service for calculating and proposing to stakeholders alternative routing for the handling of disruption considering the parameters of cost, transit time and CO ₂ emissions based on stakeholders needs and preferences.
Goal of the use case	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support the decision making for responding to disruptions • Support rerouting decisions • Support the concept of synchromodal planning
Expected impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhance visibility of alternative options along the transport corridor including all modes of transport, • Support of the synchromodal planning • Increased efficiency of transportation and the resilience of the transport corridor including the IWW
Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shippers/cargo owners • Logistics Service Providers • Transport companies

UC2.3	
Title	Digital Services for Supporting Synchromodality
Description	An inventory of digital services that may include services such as track and trace, e-documentation, traffic monitoring, cargo bundling, and on-demand warehousing, based on the availability of existing external systems that provide them. These

	services will feed CRISTAL platform to create an aggregate single point of dissemination.
Goal of the use case	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase supply chain visibility • Improve data flow and exchange among corridors' partners • Support the concept of synchromodal planning
Expected impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create visibility of services for all relevant stakeholders • Increased synchromodality • Increased and simplified data exchange
Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shippers/cargo owners • Logistics Service Providers • Transport companies

- Use cases for monitoring and evaluation

The purpose of this category of Use Cases is to showcase the services for collecting data from the implementation of technologies, SCMS operations and other external sources for feeding the observatory and provide analytics for supporting decisions and policy-making at regional level in relation to the IWW. There are three distinct Use Cases described below:

UC3.1	
Title	Infrastructure maintenance observatory
Description	A service to collect and store information coming from sensors monitoring and predicting infrastructure failures, as well as from the Digital Twins' outputs, in order to create a database of historical maintenance needs and infrastructure failures to further enhance predictive models and provide analytics for supporting decision making at regional level.
Goal of the use case	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gather in a single point infrastructure data on failures and maintenance needs • Provide analytics on the collected data based on users' needs
Expected impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased efficiency of preventive maintenance activities • Enhanced models for infrastructure maintenance requirements predictions and impact assessment • Better informed decisions on IWW infrastructure investments
Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Infrastructure authorities and managers • Public/regional authorities

UC3.2	
Title	CO₂ monitoring
Description	A service to calculate the CO ₂ emissions of available alternative routes of the corridors and compare the environmental gains of shifting freight traffic from road/rail to IWT as well as the use of the SCMS for rerouting in cases of disruptions. CO ₂ consumption will be calculated in each route and for each transport mode by applying CO ₂ calculation algorithms. The objective of this calculation will be the ultimate reduction of emissions through the increased use of CRISTAL river corridors.
Goal of the use case	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrate environmental footprint at the earlier stage of modal choice decision-making. • Enhance more sustainable cargo routing and rerouting.
Expected impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy consumption and CO₂ reduction • Increased use of IWWs • Increased use of the rail alternative in case of disruptions
Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shippers/cargo owners • Logistics Service Providers • Transport companies

UC3.3	
Title	Synchromodal cost control
Description	A service to estimate the cost of the alternative routes of the corridors and compare the cost gains/losses of shifting freight traffic from road/rail to IWT and also the cost of alternative routes/modes in the case of IWW disruptions. The objective of this calculation will be the comparison of cost and environmental (UC3.2) impacts to support shipper decisions through a synchromodal planning approach.
Goal of the use case	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explore the cost benefits of synchromodality and the SCMS. • Promote IWW transportation.
Expected impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased share of IWW transportation. • Better informed decisions on cargo rerouting in cases of disruptions
Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shippers/cargo owners • Logistics Service Providers • Transport companies

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